

PREP-IBISBA

Industrial Biotechnology Innovation and Synthetic Biology Accelerator
Preparatory Phase

Deliverable number: D8.1

A review of the EU e-Infrastructure landscape (first draft)

Planned delivery date (as in DoA): December 2020, M12

Revised delivery date (validated by the REA): August 2021, M20

Actual submission date: 2nd September 2021, M21

Workpackage: WP8

Workpackage leader: Carole Goble, UNIMAN

Deliverable leader: Carole Goble, UNIMAN

Version: 1.0

Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
CI Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

This deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871118.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Summary.....	3
2	Introduction.....	3
2.1	Methodology.....	8
3	Results.....	8
3.1	The European Open Science Cloud	8
	EOSC Governance.....	10
	EOSC Commons and Architecture	12
	EOSC Interoperability Framework and FAIR Digital Objects	16
	Implementing EOSC cross cutting services.....	18
	The EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace	19
	EOSC cross-cutting e-Infrastructure Services.....	19
	Other relevant European initiatives	20
	Mobilising National and Regional initiatives.....	20
	Projects using EOSC Portal Services	23
3.2	Thematic Research Infrastructures	24
	EOSC-Life Cluster	27
4	Conclusion.....	35
5	Partners involved in the work.....	35
6	Annexes.....	35
6.1	Annexe A: Meetings attended	35
6.2	Annexe B: EOSC Projects.....	36
6.3	Annexe C: EOSC Services	39

1 Summary

IBISBA's mission as a distributed European research infrastructure is to provide world-class cutting-edge research and innovation services enabling the development of biotechnology as a technology cornerstone of the circular bioeconomy. To achieve this, IBISBA integrates Europe's leading public-operated research infrastructure facilities into a coordinated business environment.

The H2020 PRPEP-IBISBA project is designed to finalize the design and prepare IBISBA for future operation. To achieve this the project is organized into several work packages that focus on different aspects of the infrastructure, including its business model, legal structure, and scientific and technological strategy.

In this report, we focus on the necessary coordination of IBISBA with the European technical e-Infrastructure landscape. We overview the positioning of EU infrastructures, and their plans, policies and technical solutions. The deliverable primarily focuses on the European Open Science Cloud, the thematic Research Infrastructures and Clusters serving the Biosciences, notably EOSC-Life and ELIXIR. We seek to preliminarily identify digital infrastructure that PREP-IBISBA can exploit, should align with or may contribute to.

FAIR initiatives such as FAIRsFAIR, and potential community and commercial infrastructures and their role are briefly discussed. The work was undertaken through a mixture of desk research, participation at EOSC community meetings and workshops, and interviews with key EOSC leaders and service users.

This deliverable is an outcome of Task 8.2 (Coordinate with the European technical e-Infrastructure landscape). It informs Task 8.1 (Develop a technical reference service framework, roadmap and evaluation process for the e-tools for the management of EU-IBISBA business processes and FAIR asset stewardship) and its associated deliverable 8.2 (A first technical design report) and Task 8.4 (Assemble a "sandbox" implementation of the service framework for supporting the preparatory stage of EU-IBISBA using candidate components to demonstrate and assess readiness).

2 Introduction

IBISBA is a distributed European research infrastructure that aims to provide world-class cutting-edge research and innovation services enabling the development of biotechnology as a technology cornerstone of the circular bioeconomy. To achieve this, IBISBA integrates Europe's leading public-operated research infrastructure facilities into a coordinated business environment.

As a distributed research infrastructure, EU-IBISBA will need to support a geographically distributed collection of autonomous facilities, each varying considerably in their computational and data competencies, and dedicated resources that catalogue the knowledge resources and outputs of the infrastructure's projects, serve the operation of the infrastructure and support the delivery of IBISBA's multi-facility service offerings.

Consequently, the EU-IBISBA e-Tools infrastructure outlined in Deliverable 8.2, will be a mix of core centralised shared services operated by IBISBA Central (or an IBISBA Node on behalf of IBISBA Central) and decentralised, devolved and independently operated services run by the IBISBA facilities.

The prime managed shared service is the IBISBAHub, a cataloguing and asset management system. The e-Infrastructure will require secure cloud based synchronization to the Hub and across the facilities; hosting, storage and compute capabilities; and access to and integration with external registries, repositories and tools. EU-IBISBA should use the e-infrastructure services in the EU where appropriate, and contribute to the EU e-Infrastructure landscape overall as part of the European Open Science Cloud.

Five chief and interlinked areas dominate this landscape.

1. The FAIR movement promotes the principles that data, and increasingly all research digital objects, be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, and specifically that they adhere to FAIR criteria proposed in [\(Wilkinson et al. 2016\)¹](#) and further developed by the Research Data Alliance² and projects such as FAIRsFAIR³. All e-Infrastructure activities are bound up with this parallel FAIR movement and e-Infrastructure services are expected to adhere, support and promote the FAIR data principles.

[FAIRsFAIR](#) (Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe)⁴ is the EU project that has taken “ownership” of FAIR and partners with players such as [GO-FAIR⁵](#), [CODATA⁶](#) and the [Research Data Alliance⁷](#) as well as EOSC and ESFRI projects. Other players include [ReSA⁸](#) and [Force11⁹](#) for FAIR software, and the [FAIR Digital Object Forum¹⁰](#). Numerous meetings, projects and deliverables have been produced and there is duplicated work.

Areas of activity that EU-IBISBA, and especially IBISBAHub, needs to pay attention to include:

- Recommendations for FAIR metrics/indicators for registries and repositories¹¹.
- Certification of registries and repositories for FAIRness and Trusted Repository status. The most commonly quoted certification is [Core Trust Seal¹²](#) though others include ISO16363 and DIN31644, all based on the OAIS Reference Model (ISO14721), which is more oriented to preservation than FAIRness.
- Data cataloging, metadata interoperability and integrated discovery using various metadata frameworks (DCAT, Schema.org etc.) and: the cross-walk mapping of these metadata schema¹³; attempts to create a universal pan-disciplinary metadata schema (e.g. DDI-CDI¹⁴)

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg>

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/4005598#.YQpiHEDTXZR>

⁴ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>

⁵ <https://www.go-fair.org>

⁶ <https://codata.org/>

⁷ <https://rd-alliance.org/>

⁸ <https://www.researchsoft.org/>

⁹ <https://www.force11.org/>

¹⁰ <https://fairdo.org>

¹¹ <https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2021-004/>

¹² CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2019). CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements 2020–2022 (v02.00-2020-2022). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3638211>

¹³ Ojsteršek. (2021). Crosswalk of most used metadata schemes and guidelines for metadata interoperability (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4420116>

¹⁴ <https://codata.org/ddi-cross-domain-integration-ddi-cdi-first-public-review-release/>

and mechanisms for moving metadata between data catalogues in EOSC and across the ESFRIs¹⁵.

2. European Open Science Cloud, proposed in 2016 ([European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. 2016](#))¹⁶ to build a virtual environment with open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, *across borders and scientific disciplines* by federating existing scientific data infrastructures, currently dispersed across disciplines and the EU Member States. The Core EOSC services, agenda and implementation is dominated by e-Infrastructure services funded by DG-Connect under the European Cloud Initiative ([openAIRE](#)¹⁷, [EGI](#)¹⁸, [EUDAT](#)¹⁹, [GEANT](#)²⁰, [PRACE](#)²¹). Core EOSC services cover: compute; data transfer and networking; data storage; AAI, security and privacy preservation; sharing and discovery; data management; processing and analysis and training and support.

3. EU-IBISBA's sister Thematic Life Science ESFRIs and their Clusters²² aim to federate and coordinate the organization, exchange and reuse of their data, metadata, software and services typically within scoped and concrete use cases that are more discipline specific. In effect, they are the EOSC²³. ESFRIs both use and provide generic (horizontal) e-infrastructure services and thematic services (EOSC-related, open, community or commercial). Thematic services include repositories, catalogues and registries, workflow management systems, software, thematic clouds etc. Not all services are open, but all are expected to support the FAIR principles. Although the ESFRIs are typically positioned as "users" of the horizontal and generic EOSC e-Infrastructure services, the ESFRIs also have these services, for example the ELIXIR AAI service²⁴. The most important ESFRI Cluster for EU-IBISBA is EOSC-Life, led by ELIXIR. The ESFRI for Life Science data. Infrastructures such as The European Marine Biological Resource Centre ([EMBRC](#))²⁵ and [EuroBioimaging](#)²⁶ provide facilities along the same lines as EU-IBISBA.

4. Regional, national and pan-national resources and services that form the bedrock of EOSC and the ESFRIs. National and pan-national facilities and co-operations are those that commonly provide the actual EOSC and the ESFRI services and resources. Some are subsidized by the ESFRIs and EC projects. The governance of these resources under EOSC and ESFRIs is an important topic, especially when these resources are funded outside of the EOSC and ESFRIs, have many stakeholders, and the incentives for participation are unclear.

¹⁵ Carole Goble, & Nick Juty. (2021). Analysis of existing research data cataloguing efforts towards integrated discovery. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4693217>

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/directorate-general-research-and-innovation_en

¹⁷ <http://openaire.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://www.egi.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://eudat.eu/>

²⁰ <https://www.geant.org/>

²¹ <https://prace-ri.eu/>

²² <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>, <https://lifescience-ri.eu/>

²³ <https://zenodo.org/record/3675081#.YQpizkDTXZQ>

²⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/services/compute/aai>

²⁵ <https://www.embrc.eu/>

²⁶ <https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/>

5. **Open, community and commercial services** run in parallel to, with varying degrees of independence from the services above. Outside the bubble of EOSC and the ESFRIs, the vast majority of researchers and developers routinely use software hosting, container hosting, proprietary build systems, synchronization and sharing services etc. A particular example is the [Cloud Storage Services for Synchronization and Sharing \(CS3\) community](#)²⁷ funded in the EU [C₃MESH₄OEOSC](#)²⁸ project to develop standard APIs and become integrated into the EOSC, providing a Pan-European natively FAIR and GDPR compliant data storage and sharing fabric. Open source examples include: the [Common Workflow Language](#)²⁹, workflow management systems such as [Nextflow](#)³⁰ and [Galaxy](#)³¹; notebooks such as [Jupyter Notebook](#)³² and [Google Colaboratory](#)³³; compute services such as [Kubernetes](#)³⁴, [SLURM](#)³⁵ and [OpenStack](#)³⁶; research object packaging like [RO-Crate](#)³⁷; container registries and hosting such as [Dockstore](#)³⁸ and [Quay.io](#)³⁹; cloud synchronization and sharing services like [Owncloud](#)⁴⁰; open source data management like [iRODS](#)⁴¹, [DataVerse](#)⁴², and [InvenioRDM](#)⁴³; and cataloguing systems like [FAIRDOM-SEEK](#)⁴⁴.

Commercial or semi-commercial examples include: [GitHub](#)⁴⁵, [Docker](#)⁴⁶, [Singularity](#)⁴⁷, [DockerHub](#)⁴⁸, [Dropbox](#)⁴⁹, [AWS](#)⁵⁰, [Google Cloud Platform](#)⁵¹, [Nextcloud](#)⁵², [KNIME](#)⁵³ etc. Commercial providers offer “Freemium” services, that is a pricing strategy by which a basic product or service is provided free of charge, but money (a premium) is charged for additional features, services, or virtual (online) or physical (offline) goods that expand the functionality of the free version of the software. A trend is to move free services to charged services in terms of use (see DockerHub’s new terms of use for docker images and autobuilds).

²⁷ <https://www.cs3community.org/>

²⁸ <https://cs3mesh4eosc.eu/>

²⁹ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.nextflow.io/>

³¹ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

³² <https://jupyter.org/>

³³ <https://colab.research.google.com/notebooks/>

³⁴ <https://kubernetes.io/>

³⁵ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

³⁶ <https://ubuntu.com/openstack>

³⁷ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

³⁸ <https://dockstore.org/>

³⁹ <https://quay.io/>

⁴⁰ <https://owncloud.com/>

⁴¹ <https://irods.org/>

⁴² <https://dataverse.org/>

⁴³ <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>

⁴⁴ <https://seek4science.org/>

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.docker.com/>

⁴⁷ <https://sylabs.io/singularity/>

⁴⁸ <https://hub.docker.com/>

⁴⁹ <http://dropbox.com/>

⁵⁰ <https://aws.amazon.com/>

⁵¹ <https://cloud.google.com/>

⁵² <https://nextcloud.com/>

⁵³ <https://www.knime.com/>

Many of these have been adopted by EOSC and ESFRIs and will be referenced in the document.

EU-IBISBA needs to carefully choose its software, container image hosting and build environments to get the benefit of Freemium services with the options to pivot when terms of use change.

Figure 1: the European e-Infrastructure jigsaw

Overarching these are the **particular perspectives of the European Commission**: the promotion of Open Science, coordinated optimized investment, cross-disciplinary research, certification and metrics and the notion of an EOSC “marketplace” for all researchers. The first two are understandable. The last three are more questionable and often lead to strategic decisions and operational investments that are more to do with these political ambitions than research practice or need. For example: the CDI-DDI framework⁵⁴ for cross-disciplinary catalogue interoperability championed by CODATA has yet to show a concrete and convincing use case with the effort; responses to the public SRIA consultation in 2020⁵⁵ rated certification and metrics and landscape monitoring as low priority; and the EOSCHub Conference 2020 session on ESFRI Clusters and EOSC highlighted the universal inappropriateness of a “marketplace” metaphor for research infrastructures. Yet these misgivings in the community and “at the coalface” have made little impact. EU-IBISBA will need to carefully monitor developments.

This deliverable focuses on the e-Infrastructure landscape of the **European Open Science Cloud and the ESFRIs**, and references to regional, open community and commercial services. References to FAIR principles, policy and implementation will be made where appropriate.

A number of recommendations are made for EU-IBISBA, including recommended engagements, and further investigations. This deliverable chiefly informs Deliverable D8.2, A first technical design report: reference service framework, roadmap and evaluation process, and tasks 8.2 and 8.4. EU-IBISBA’s policy and recommendations for practice for FAIR Compliance will be covered in Deliverable D8.2.

⁵⁴ <https://codata.org/ddi-cross-domain-integration-ddi-cdi-first-public-review-release/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/open-consultation-eosc-strategic-research-and-innovation-agenda>

2.1 Methodology

The work was undertaken through a mixture of desk research, participation at EOSC community meetings & workshops, and interviews with key EOSC leaders and service users. Authors are members of EOSC Life Science Cluster [EOSC-Life](#)⁵⁶, the ESFRI for Life Science data [ELIXIR](#)⁵⁷ and [EOSC-Enhance](#)⁵⁸ which is developing the EOSC Service Catalogue and Portal. Annexe A lists relevant meetings. Annexe B lists European Projects referenced in the deliverable.

3 Results

3.1 The European Open Science Cloud

The EOSC vision as set out by the High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud in 2016⁵⁹ is to offer European researchers a virtual environment with open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research digital objects (like publications, data, and software), across borders and scientific disciplines by federating existing scientific data infrastructures, currently dispersed across disciplines and the EU Member States, and by following the FAIR data principles. This European contribution to a “Web of FAIR Data and Related Services for Science” aims to enhance the possibilities for researchers to find, share and reuse publications, data, and software leading to new insights and innovations, higher research productivity and improved reproducibility in science. A strong emphasis is placed on Open Science and Open Innovation⁶⁰. The EOSC supports the EC’s [Open Science policy](#)⁶¹ and the EC’s [European Data Strategy](#)⁶² recognizes the EOSC as the nucleus for a science, research and innovation data space which will become articulated with the 9 sectoral data spaces foreseen by the strategy.

⁵⁶ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

⁵⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

⁵⁸ <https://eosc-portal.eu/enhance>

⁵⁹ Realising the European Open Science Cloud First report and recommendations of the Commission High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud (2016)

https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/realising_the_european_open_science_cloud_2016.pdf

⁶⁰ Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World – a vision for Europe (2016) <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/open-innovation-open-science-open-world-vision-europe>

⁶¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/open-science>

⁶² https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en

Figure 2: European Open Science Cloud Objectives Tree from EOSC SRIA

Consultations with scientific and institutional stakeholders in 2016 and 2017 led to an [EOSC Declaration](#)⁶³ endorsed by more than 70 institutions. A final report and recommendations⁶⁴ set out the strategy. The [EOSC implementation roadmap](#)⁶⁵ described six action lines for the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud with specific examples and related milestones: for Architecture, Data, Services, Access and Interfaces, Rules and Governance. A range of projects⁶⁶ were funded in the INFRA calls to support this roadmap, some referenced by this report.

The EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda⁶⁷ defines the general framework for future strategic research, development and innovation activities in relation to the EOSC, to be further defined in the context of the EOSC European Partnership⁶⁸. The SRIA emphasises Open Science (Figure 2) and introduces a timetable (Figure 3).

⁶³ EOSC Declaration https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/eosc_declaration.pdf.

⁶⁴ European Commission (2018). Prompting an EOSC in practice. Final report and recommendations of the Commission 2nd High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) <http://doi.org/10.2777/112658>.

⁶⁵ European Commission (2019). European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Strategic Implementation Plan <https://doi.org/10.2777/202370>

⁶⁶ <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc-projects>

⁶⁷ <https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC-SRIA-V09.pdf>

⁶⁸ <https://eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/eosc-sria-strategic-research-innovation-agenda-version-09>

Stage 1 (2021–2022): Development towards added value from a functional federation of infrastructures

Enabling the **European Open Science Cloud operations (the EOSC-Core)** to provide necessary core functions of the Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE) that allow federation of existing and future infrastructures, with associated rules of engagement and governance that provision growth and expansion in the following stages.

Stage 2 (2023–2024): Expansion to production that generates added value

Expanding and building the core data infrastructure to support the full cycle of workflows for scientific research in key thematic areas. During this period, work to build on pilots/demonstrators and to link EOSC beyond the research communities to the wider public sector and the private sector will begin.

Stage 3 (2025–2027 and beyond): Expansion to develop impact from Open Science

Deployment of federated research infrastructures for European researchers with functionality that provisions actors from multiple communities to deliver impactful Open Science. In addition to European infrastructures, the national research infrastructures delivered from the Member States and Associated Countries in particular will help in this expansion phase.

Figure 3: EOSC SRIA Roadmap

EOSC Governance

In late 2020 a stakeholder-driven [EOSC governance structure](#)⁶⁹ centred on the **EOSC Association, an EOSC Partnership and EOSC Associates** was established⁷⁰. The EOSC Association was legally constituted and a [co-programmed European Partnership under Horizon Europe from 2021](#)⁷¹ proposed as the means to bring together institutional, national and European initiatives and engage all relevant stakeholders to co-design and deploy a **European Research Data Commons** where data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR). The aim is that by 2025 EOSC operations will be deployed to serve EU researchers.

Currently the Association has 118 members⁷², of which 21 are nationally mandated organisations, and 69 observers. These members and observers include research funding organisations, research performing organisations, service providing organisations, and **must be a legal entity**. Members have voting rights and observers do not⁷³. Members and observers pay an annual membership fee. Currently this is set at 10Keuro per annum for Members and 2K for Observers. The prospect is that the fee will be reduced to 5K euro per annum. Membership includes EMBL, which blocks ELIXIR joining as a member in its own right as it is legally an EMBL special project. Membership includes INRIA and INRAE, but not many organisations from EU-IBISBA, and few ESFRIs.

The [EOSC Secretariat](#)⁷⁴ Coordination and Support Action supports the EOSC Governance, running a series of open calls for co-creation projects (42 funded so far) enable EOSC stakeholders to

⁶⁹<https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-governance>

⁷⁰https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/funding/documents/ec_rtd_he-partnership-open-science-cloud-eosc.pdf

⁷¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe/european-partnerships-horizon-europe/candidates-across-themes_en

⁷² <https://www.eosc.eu/members>

⁷³ European Open Science Cloud Association. (02/07/2020). EOSC AISBL Statutes.

https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_statutes.pdf

⁷⁴ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/about/eosc-secretariat-consortium>

contribute⁷⁵[Working Groups](#)⁷⁶ worked towards community-sourced approach and provided valuable input into the development of EOSC. Some important documents emerged, including the [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#)⁷⁷ which has influenced Horizon Europe calls. Following on, the EOSC Association has established [five Advisory Groups](#)⁷⁸ focusing on overarching themes that are important for the realisation of EOSC, which consist of Task Forces working on specific topics - that largely cover the same ground as the previous working groups (Table 1). Membership applications closed on 30th July 2021 and are weighted in favour of Association members and observers.

EOSC Secretariat Working Groups 2018-2020	EOSC Association Task force 2021-2025
<p>FAIR⁷⁹: Implementing the FAIR data principles by defining the corresponding requirements for the development of EOSC services, to foster cross-disciplinary interoperability, which is a particular obsession of the Commission. FAIR principles, policy and implementation will be discussed where appropriate.</p>	<p>Advisory Group - Metadata and Data Quality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● TF FAIR Metrics and Data Quality⁸⁰ ● TF Semantic Interoperability⁸¹ <p><i>Relevant to EU-IBISBA proposed technical framework addressed in Deliverable 8.2</i></p>
<p>Architecture⁸²: Defining the technical framework required to enable and sustain an evolving EOSC federation of systems. As EOSC is a federation of existing and planned research data infrastructures, it has a federating core and a variety of federated research data infrastructures committed to providing services as part of the EOSC (for example PIDs and AAI), and promotes the notion of FAIR Digital Objects.</p>	<p>Advisory Group - Technical Challenges on EOSC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● TF AAI Architecture⁸³ ● TF Infrastructure for Quality Research Software⁸⁴ ● TF Technical Interoperability of Data and Services⁸⁵ <p><i>Relevant to EU-IBISBA proposed technical framework addressed in Deliverable 8.2</i></p>
<p>Skills and Training⁸⁶: Providing a framework for a sustainable training infrastructure to support EOSC in all its phases and ensure its uptake, for example FAIR competency frameworks.</p>	<p>Advisory Group - Research Careers and Curricula</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● TF Data Stewardship Curricula and Career Paths⁸⁷ ● TF Research Careers, Recognition, and Credit⁸⁸

⁷⁵ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/funding-opportunities/list-approved-co-creation-activities>

⁷⁶ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-working-groups>

⁷⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190308283>

⁷⁸ <https://www.eosc.eu/news/draft-charters-eosc-association-task-forces-published>

⁷⁹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/fair-working-group>

⁸⁰ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tffairmetricsanddataquality_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁸¹ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfsemanticinteroperability_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁸² <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/architecture-working-group>

⁸³ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfaaiarchitecture_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁸⁴ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfinfrastructureforqualityresearchsoftware_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁸⁵ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tftechnicalinteroperabilityofdataandservices_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁸⁶ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/skills-training-working-group>

⁸⁷ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfdastewardshipcurriculaandcareerpaths_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁸⁸ https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfresearchcareersrecognitionandcredit_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TF Upskilling Countries to Engage in EOSC⁸⁹ <p><i>EU-IBISBA e-Tools and data stewardship training is addressed in Deliverable 8.3.</i></p>
<p>Rules of participation⁹⁰: Designing the Rules of Participation in the EOSC federation and in the Governance defining the rights and obligations between users, providers and operators.</p> <p>Landscape⁹¹: Mapping existing research infrastructures which are the candidates to be part of the “EOSC federation” particularly leveraging the INFRAEOSC-5b regional projects⁹². National initiatives are among the key elements for the creation of an inclusive and sustainable EOSC and its realisation lies in the willingness of Member States, Associated Countries and their resources to participate and collaborate, and seamless, transnational access to nationally held infrastructures.</p>	<p>Advisory Group - Implementation of EOSC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TF PID Policy and Implementation⁹³ • TF Researcher Engagement and Adoption⁹⁴ • TF Rules of Participation Compliance Monitoring⁹⁵ <p><i>Rules of participation apply to EU-IBISBA as we position ourselves to use and potentially provide EOSC services.</i></p> <p><i>The majority of EU-IBISBA data resources will reside at the national level and we will need to use EOSC services provided at the national level</i></p>
<p>Sustainability⁹⁶: Providing a set of recommendations concerning the implementation of the EOSC Association and Partnership.</p>	<p>Advisory Group - Sustaining EOSC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TF Defining Funding Models for EOSC⁹⁷ • TF Long-Term Data Preservation⁹⁸

Table 1: EOSC WGs, AGs and TFs

As a Research Infrastructure on the ESFRI Roadmap, EU-IBISBA should seek to become an EOSC Association Member as soon as it has its legal entity status. Meanwhile, EU-IBISBA should audit its member organisations that are members and lobby through these. Where possible individuals should seek to engage with the Task Forces.

EOSC Commons and Architecture

The EOSC is not a single “thing” like the Amazon or Google Cloud. It doesn’t have a single interface and it's not actually a cloud platform. Barend Mons, the convening chair of the High Level Expert Group that conceived the EOSC joked that it is not European (encompassing many services outside of Europe); it is not Open, because data may not always be able to be shared openly across

⁸⁹https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfupskillingcountriestoengageineosc_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁹⁰ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/rules-participation-working-group>

⁹¹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/landscape-working-group>

⁹² <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/communities/eosc-regional-projects>

⁹³https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfpidpolicyandimplementation_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁹⁴https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfresearcherengagementandadoption_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁹⁵https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfrulesofparticipationcompliancemonitoring_draftcharter_20210614_0.pdf

⁹⁶ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/sustainability-working-group>

⁹⁷https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tfdefiningfundingmodelsforeosc_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

⁹⁸https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/tfcharters/eosca_tflongtermdatapreservation_draftcharter_20210614.pdf

organisational borders due to legal constraints ; it is not solely serving Science but all research including the humanities; and it not a Cloud service with a single interface, like AWS or GPC (though cloud services are part of it). EOSC is more like a **Commons**, as defined by Bob Grossman, because it brings together (or co-locates) data with cloud computing infrastructure and commonly used software services, tools & applications for managing, analyzing and sharing data to create an interoperable resource for a research community⁹⁹. It is noted that in the EOSC Partnership the term **European Research Data Commons** is used instead.

EOSC is a federation of generic and thematic services and resources and a federation of systems or a “system of systems”. Figure 4, adapted from the RI ENVRIplus (now part of the ENVRI-FAIR Cluster), illustrates this. Although for political purposes, the European Commission prefers to separate, on one hand, underpinning, cross-cutting services and, on the other hand, research infrastructure and clusters, for practical purposes many research infrastructure are internalizing e-infrastructure services.

Figure 4: The EOSC federation should combine thematic RI and generic e-Infrastructure services (courtesy of MC)

The SRIA also envisages EOSC as a federation of infrastructures, forming a Web of FAIR Digital Objects and Related Services for Science and states that “**the envisioned EOSC can only be realised in a decentralised federated way**”. The FAIR principles and metadata standards act as guidelines for interoperability and facilitate maximum sharing and exploitation of research by the academic, private and public sectors. EOSC is expected to grow through a series of iterations, adding more functionalities and services for a wider user base and satisfying a broader range of use cases.

A **Minimal Viable EOSC framework** is proposed based on three layers (Figure 5, Table 2): (i) the federating core (EOSC-Core), (iii) a service layer comprising common services and thematic services

⁹⁹ Robert Grossman, Allison Heath, Mark Murphy, Maria Patterson, and Walt Wells, “A Case for Data Commons: Toward Data Science as a Service,” *Computing in Science & Engineering* 18(5) (2016): 10–20.

(EOSC-Exchange); and (iii) a data federation of existing and planned research data infrastructures. Figure 6 gives the expected services of a MVE.

Figure 5: Minimal Viable EOSC framework from EOSC Interoperability Framework

Layer	Mechanisms & Frameworks	Services compliant with EOSC Policies & Rules of Participation
<p>The EOSC-Core Basic elements to operate and provide the means to discover, share, access and reuse data and services in a reliable manner. Long-term sustainability</p>	<p><i>PID Framework</i> naming and locating documents, data, software and services; <i>Data access framework</i> discovery of and access to documents, data, software and services; <i>Authentication and Authorization Interoperability (AAI) framework</i> for managing user identity and access. <i>Metadata framework</i> <i>Service management & access framework</i> <i>Open metrics framework</i> <i>Security framework</i> <i>Support framework</i></p>	<p>Repositories & Registries complying with an open charter that describe what users can expect from the service, such as descriptions of the content with rich, community-defined and FAIR metadata, sustainability commitments, quality goals, etc. Authentication and authorisation rules and services for allowing access by users. Persistent identifiers (PID) services Metadata services describing the content available in order, for example, to allow discovery by end users; Open Application programming interfaces (APIs) for access by machines, and to allow the development of applications using the content. Networking connectivity with commitments on upload and download capabilities;</p>

<p>The EOSC-Exchange builds on the EOSC-Core to ensure that a rich set of services (common and thematic), exploiting FAIR data and encouraging its reuse, are available to publicly funded researchers.</p>	<p>Rivalrous services, such as those that store, preserve or transport research data as well as those that compute against it.</p> <p>It is unclear if a thematic repository is a thematic service or a EOSC Core Service.</p>	<p>Common services May not be shared by all stakeholders, may be already developed and can be adopted by others; e.g archival services</p> <p>Thematic services Covers all the services that communities need to develop to contribute to the EOSC ecosystem. These services are delivered to researchers and all stakeholders to enhance their working environment. They are built using the relevant elements of the federating core (EOSC-Core) and may leverage common services.</p>
<p>Federated Data of existing and planned research data infrastructures</p> <p>The FAIR principles and metadata standards enable the federation of existing and planned research data infrastructures, adding a "soft overlay" to connect them and forming a Web of FAIR Data and Services.</p>	<p>Underlying framework based on commonly agreed, minimum standards and maximum freedom to operate with agility. global and interdisciplinary interoperability. access points must have an API for machine to enable innovative value-adding services to be developed</p> <p>metadata frameworks such as Bioschemas and RO-Crate have a key role to play.</p>	<p>Multiple and often thematic entry points to the "EOSC environment" Web portals, services, tools, resources Users find content and related services, learn about commonly adopted approaches, formats, standards and EOSC Rules of Participation, register their resources.</p> <p>EOSC Portal and Service Catalogue developed by EOSC Enhance and EOSC Future</p>

Table 2: A Minimal Viable EOSC framework layers

Figure 6: Envisioned Minimal Viable EOSC by the Architecture WG,
from EOSC Interoperability Framework

The development of the MVE and its services should be incorporated into the technical digital framework for EU-IBISBA reported in Deliverable 8.2, and its proposed components mapped to the services outlined.

EOSC Interoperability Framework and FAIR Digital Objects

Achieving interoperability within EOSC is essential in order for the federation of services that will compose EOSC to provide added value for service users. The [EOSC Interoperability Framework](#)¹⁰⁰, was developed by the Interoperability Task Force of the EOSC Executive Board FAIR Working Group, with participation from the Architecture WG and published in early 2021. It makes several important points that resonate with EU-IBISBA:

- Interoperability applies to the many other research artefacts that may be used in the context of research activity, such as software code, scientific workflows, laboratory protocols, open hardware designs, etc, as well as data;
- An analysis of existing metadata models and an initial set of crosswalks;
- Services and e-infrastructures must be as interoperable as possible, as well as data, and introducing 4 layers of interoperability: technical, semantic, organisational and legal (Figure 7);
- A proposal for the management of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) in the context of EOSC;
- A proposal for a reference architecture for the EOSC Interoperability Framework that is inspired by and extends the European Interoperability Reference Architecture (EIRA), identifying the main building blocks required.

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/achieving-interoperability-eosc-interoperability-framework>

FAIR Digital Objects were highlighted in the EC's [Turning FAIR Into Reality](#)¹⁰¹ 2018 report and a FDO framework proposed¹⁰². The FAIR Digital Objects Forum has been established, spinning out from the RDA Data Fabric Interest Group. EU-IBISBA members have attended and presented at meetings of both, and are attempting to join FDOForum working groups, although the forum is not operated as an open community. [RO-Crate](#)¹⁰³ [[Soiland-Reyes et al 2021](#)¹⁰⁴] is being developed as a community standard to practically achieve FAIR packaging of such research objects with their structured metadata. It is based on well-established Web standards, using JSON-LD with [schema.org](#)¹⁰⁵ for its common metadata representation, but extensible with domain-specific vocabularies in a growing range of specialized RO-Crate profiles. These include, for example earth sciences [[Corcho et al 2021](#)¹⁰⁶] and computational workflows [[Goble et al 2021](#)¹⁰⁷] in the ELIXIR Tools platform. RO-Crate has been proposed for the implementation of FAIR Digital Objects¹⁰⁸ on the World Wide Web as a common representation of the FDO Metadata objects foreseen by the FDO Framework. Combined with FAIR Signposting¹⁰⁹ for resolving persistent identifiers to the FDO components these RO-Crates are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable by machines to both create and obtain the information they need to function.

ELIXIR Tools Platform and the EOSC-Life Workflow Collaboratory, EU projects RELIANCE, [CS3MESH4EOSC](#)¹¹⁰ are implementing RO-Crate Research Objects. These are used for a range of purposes, including reporting and reproducibility, exchange between services, archiving and publication, and citation.

EU-IBISBA is already implementing RO-Crate for IBISBAHub, inherited from its underlying FAIRDOM-SEEK platform, which is a reference implementation for RO-Crate, and also as an exchange mechanism with the EOSC-Life Workflow Collaboratory and for export to registries such as OpenAIRE and WorkflowHub and repositories such as Zenodo and DataVerse.

¹⁰¹ <http://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

¹⁰² De Smedt, K., Koureas, D., & Wittenburg, P. (2020). FAIR Digital Objects for Science: From Data Pieces to Actionable Knowledge Units. *Publications*, 8(2), 21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications8020021>

¹⁰³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹⁰⁴ <https://stain.github.io/ro-crate-paper/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://schema.org/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4913285>

¹⁰⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4605654>

¹⁰⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5060284>

¹⁰⁹ <https://signposting.org/FAIR/>

¹¹⁰ <https://cs3mesh4eosc.eu/>

Layer	Recommendation
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Specifications for EOSC Services. • A common security and privacy framework (including Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure). • Easy-to-understand Service-Level Agreements for all EOSC resource providers. • Easy access to data sources available in different formats. • Coarse-grained and fine-grained dataset (and other research object) search tools. • A clear EOSC PID policy.
Semantic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear and precise, publicly-available definitions for all concepts, metadata and data schemas. • Semantic artefacts preferably with open licenses. • Associated documentation for semantic artefacts. • Repositories of semantic artefacts, rules with a clear governance framework. • A minimum metadata model (and crosswalks) to ease discovery over existing federated research data and metadata. • Extensibility options to allow for disciplinary metadata. • Clear protocols and building blocks for the federation/harvesting of semantic artefacts catalogues.
Organisational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability-focused rules of participation recommendations. • Usage recommendations of standardised data formats and/or vocabularies, and with their corresponding metadata. • A clear management of permanent organisation names and functions.
Legal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised human and machine-readable licenses, with a centralised source of knowledge and support on copyright and licenses. • Permissive licenses for metadata (and preferably for data, whenever possible). And CC0 preferred over CC BY 4.0. • Identification of different parts of a dataset with different licenses. • Clearly marked instances of expired or inexistent copyright, as well as for orphan data. • A clear list of EOSC-recommended licenses and their compatibility with Member States' recommended licenses. • Tracking of license evolution over time for datasets. • Harmonised policy and guidance to dealing with cases where patent filing or trade secrets may be compromised by disclosure. • GDPR-compliance for personal data. • Additional restrictions on access and use of data only applied in cases of applicable legislation or legitimate reasons. • Harmonised terms of use across repositories • Alignment between Member States national legislations and EOSC.

Figure 7 Four layers of interoperability as presented in the EOSC Interoperability Framework

Implementing EOSC cross cutting services

Cloud computing and storage services, data handling and data analysis services, as well as federating services, are vital to an EOSC infrastructure. Several interoperability challenges and non-technical barriers have to be overcome to provide seamless access to distributed cloud computing resources, data storage, repository solutions and to enable mobility of modeling and data analysis codes between infrastructures. Common policies have to be established, at the regional, national, and European levels and a lightweight management of the horizontal service layer has to be put into place.

The EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace

Table 2 references the [EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace¹¹¹](#), developed by a series of dedicated EOSC projects. It will be developed further in the H2020 [EOSC Future¹¹²](#) H2020. The EOSC Portal is part of the EOSC implementation roadmap as one of the expected “federating core” services. It has been conceived to “provide a European delivery channel connecting the demand-side and the supply-side of the EOSC and all its stakeholders.”

A very small number of ESFRIs are listed as service providers¹¹³. Only seven RIs are referenced specifically in the Marketplace catalogue as providers and/or related RIs and platforms: CESSDA, CLARIN, ELIXIR, INFRAFRONTIER, INSTRUCT ERIC, LifeWatch, and PRACE. The quality of tagging and curation is poor which gives a hit and miss discovery experience.

The Marketplace has been used to identify EU-IBISBA compute and data service. EU-IBISBA will need to register IBISBAHub as an EOSC Service once EU-IBISBA is a legal entity. Meanwhile we have registered the Hub in the ELIXIR thematic service catalogue FAIRSharing and propose to use this as well as ELIXIR’s Bio.tools and WorkflowHub for registering and discovering tools, repositories and registries.

EOSC cross-cutting e-Infrastructure Services

The Core EOSC services, agenda and implementation is dominated by e-Infrastructure services funded by DG-Connect under the European Cloud Initiative (openAIRE, FREYA, EGI, EUDAT, GEANT, PRACE). Core EOSC services cover: compute; data storage and data management; sharing and discovery; AAI, security and privacy preservation; processing and analysis; data transfer and networking; and training and support.

The recently launched H2020 [EOSC-Future project¹¹⁴](#) (40million euro) aims to implement the MVE layers, drawing in these partners plus representation from the ESFRI. The EOSC Future project “will develop an environment with interoperable research data sets and other research outputs including publications and code, professional data services, and access to resources such as compute and storage and services like data discovery and archive. It will create a so-called ‘system of systems’ that will support European researchers in managing the entire lifecycle of data: from sharing, managing and exploiting their own data to discovering, re-using and recombining the data sets of others”.

Implementation projects in flight under the call “H2020-INFRAEOSC-07-2020: Increasing the service offer of the EOSC Portal” continues funding to several of these funded e-Infrastructures service providers. A new round of Horizon Europe projects implementing EOSC build on the H2020 programme, but the emphasis is now lifting TRL5 and higher to at least TRL7 or higher. In other words, delivering production systems and services rather than pilots. The first submissions are due 23 Sept 2021.

The tendency is for the Thematic Research Infrastructures to implement these MVE layers themselves, and build “mini-EOSCs” directly relevant to their communities, building on decades of

¹¹¹ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

¹¹² <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

¹¹³ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/>

¹¹⁴ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

community developed production infrastructure. Thematic RIs may partner directly with the e-Infrastructure service providers, or use other open source or commercial providers; they design their thematic services to use off the shelf compute and data technologies and open standards to avoid provider lock-in. We will discuss this in Section 3. Annexe C summaries high profile EU e-Infrastructure services and service providers.

Other relevant European initiatives

Other initiatives that EU-IBISBA needs to be aware of are highlighted below.

[EU HPC Centres of Excellence¹¹⁵](#) There are 15 European Centres of Excellence for High Performance Computing applications that promote the use of upcoming exascale and extreme performance computing capabilities and scale up existing parallel codes towards exascale scaling performance, and address the skills gap in computational science in the targeted domains by specialized trainings for increased adoption of advanced HPC in industry and academia. *EU-IBISBA collaborates with the BioExcel CoE on common standards for computational workflows (RO-Crate, CWL, Bioschemas) and both use the EOSC-Life Workflow Collaboratory.*

[A European Strategy for data¹¹⁶](#) which aims at creating a single market for data that will ensure Europe's global competitiveness and data sovereignty. **Common European Data Spaces** will ensure that more data becomes available for use in the economy and society, while keeping the companies and individuals who generate the data in control. *Of the nine proposed data spaces, two appear relevant to EU-IBISBA: (i) an Industrial data space, to support the competitiveness and performance of the EU's industry; and (ii) a Green Deal data space, to use the major potential of data in support of the Green Deal priority actions on issues such as climate change, circular economy, pollution, biodiversity, and deforestation.*

[Excellence and trust in artificial intelligence¹¹⁷](#) which focuses on building confidence in trustworthy artificial intelligence in better healthcare, safer and cleaner transport, *more efficient manufacturing, and cheaper and more sustainable energy.*

Mobilising National and Regional initiatives

The reality of EOSC is that it is not "one cloud" like AWS or GCP, but a concept to be realised by stitching together and accessing national initiatives. The majority of EU-IBISBA data resources will reside at the national level and need to use EOSC services provided at the national level. The services existing at national/regional level need to be identified, because those may be beneficial for the national communities and, for their ability to scale at European level by interconnecting with those in EOSC. Thus, national initiatives are among the key elements for the creation of an inclusive and sustainable EOSC. When seeking EOSC partnerships for EU-IBISBA the national and regional perspective will be taken into account with respect to IBISBA National Nodes.

¹¹⁵ <https://www.hpccoe.eu/eu-hpc-centres-of-excellence2/>

¹¹⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>

¹¹⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/excellence-trust-artificial-intelligence>

Four regional projects were funded in 2019 under INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019 to mobilise National and Regional initiatives to expand EOSC throughout Europe. Together these regional projects cover 36 countries (PREP-IBISBA countries underlined).

- [EOSC-Nordic¹¹⁸](#): Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway and Sweden.
- [EOSC-Pillar¹¹⁹](#): Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy.
- [EOSC-Synergy¹²⁰](#): Czech Republic, Germany, the Netherlands, Portugal, Poland, Slovakia, Spain, and the United Kingdom.
- [NI4OS-Europe¹²¹](#): Albania, Armenia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia and Slovenia.

A Collaboration Agreement exists between these four projects ([EOSC-Pillar¹²²](#), [EOSC-synergy¹²³](#), [EOSC-Nordic¹²⁴](#), [NI4OS-Europe¹²⁵](#)), [ExPaNDS¹²⁶](#), [EOSCSecretariat.eu¹²⁷](#), and [FAIRsFAIR¹²⁸](#). All the regional projects focus on supporting coordination, harmonisation and alignment of national open science policies and practices related to research data services with EOSC. The promotion of FAIR data principles is one of the key aspects of this process, and all the projects are expected to both facilitate training and engagement with regional open science circles, linking with the broader EOSC community. Each has undertaken surveys of their regions to provide overviews of the policies, practices, roadmaps, and strategies around open science, FAIR principles, EOSC service onboarding, interoperability frameworks and training. Issues cover funding, procuring, providing, accessing, and sharing of services and resources. The availability or state of preparedness of national research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures to offer transnational access, and procurement of services and resources are reviewed.

EOSC-Pillar produced a [National Initiatives Survey¹²⁹](#) cross-section study targeting funding bodies, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures and universities; and EOSC-Synergy produced a collection of [National EOSC Landscape reports¹³⁰](#) that aim to provide an overview of the policies, practices, roadmaps, and strategies around funding, procuring, providing, and transnational access of services

¹¹⁸ <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>

¹²⁰ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

¹²¹ <https://ni4os.eu/>

¹²² <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>

¹²³ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

¹²⁴ <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

¹²⁵ <https://ni4os.eu/>

¹²⁶ <https://expands.eu/>

¹²⁷ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/>

¹²⁸ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>

¹²⁹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/eosc-pillar-national-initiatives-survey-work-package>

¹³⁰ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/national-eosc-landscapes/>

and resources in the EOSC scope. The EOSC Secretariat [compiled position papers on EOSC](#)¹³¹, a [Landscape of EOSC-related infrastructures and initiatives](#)¹³² as well as the [country sheets analysis](#)¹³³.

EOSC readiness is loosely defined as having relevant *policies* (rather than technical capability) in place or in the planning stage related to OS, Open Access, Open Data and Open Learning at the national level to foster an ecosystem that will enable the EOSC vision. Reports highlight the following needs, which have all been taken up in the EOSC Partnership:

- A support mechanism and best practices to facilitate convergence and alignment between European, national and regional structures and initiatives, notably convergence on: a common way of identifying, authenticating, and authorising users (AAI) across Europe, long-term archiving of large quantities of open data coupled to high-performance storage and computing resources. *IBISBA will need to carefully monitor and if necessary contribute to this converge as our digital infrastructure will need to comply. We must choose EOSC aligned services*
- Incentives, prerequisites, training, awareness-raising and user-friendly onboarding procedure for all primary stakeholder groups and services for the uptake of EOSC, addressing the different levels of readiness across Europe in terms of open science, FAIR and EOSC understanding. *IBISBA will chiefly limit its EOSC awareness to partners delivering the digital infrastructure or providing computational modular services.*
- The definition of the EOSC standard interfaces, evaluating their adoption locally in order to maximise interoperability between EOSC services and those offered by national RIs. *IBISBA will need to carefully monitor and if necessary contribute to standard interfaces as our digital infrastructure will need to comply.*
- Standardisation and certification for collaboration on the federation of existing data catalogues and services, and common standards for FAIR data and services. *IBISBAHub will need to comply to standardization and seek certification.*
- The EOSC legal entity, its governance, and operation to function as a *federation* with clear rules of participation, and that its governance addresses: national open science policies, the delivery of horizontal services, access to resources in a transnational environment, legal challenges associated with the cross-border sharing of resources, and guarantees for the long-term sustainability of the coordination. EU-IBISBA should seek to become a member of the EOSC Association and participate in active Task Forces.

In all of the countries reviewed there are available infrastructures that may be federated, or made available. **Most made clear that the infrastructures could not as yet be considered “EOSC ready”, and that investment would be needed to enhance EOSC readiness.** Most are still at the planning stage. A FAIRsFAIR survey of HEI¹³⁴ suggests that Universities can see potential benefits of EOSC such as facilitating collaborative research and increasing the visibility of research carried out, but overall awareness of EOSC tends to be concentrated among University leadership and research data support staff rather than among research staff. The majority of those responding to the FAIRsFAIR survey

¹³¹ https://zenodo.org/record/3831561#.X_RhdBbgrZQ

¹³² <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9c7f3c1e-2aea-11eb-9d7e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-173604556>

¹³³ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/95e4a900-2a21-11eb-9d7e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-173316815>

¹³⁴ Stoy, L. Saenen, B. Davidson, J. Engelhardt, C. Gaillard, V. (2020). D7.1 FAIR in European Higher Education (Version 1.0_draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3629682>

state that within the HEIs there is limited awareness of EOSC and its potential benefits, a lack of use cases and limited capacity in most HEIs to use EOSC services, requiring improved engagement of HEIs with the EOSC through onboarding support and the development of clear use cases. *Where appropriate, IBISBA needs to raise EOSC awareness in its facilities and National Nodes, and their institutions.*

The EU-IBISBA facilities have limited awareness of EOSC. It is likely that awareness will be chiefly the responsibility of IBISBA Central, lead e-Infrastructure providers and operators. Therefore, EU-IBISBA will need to carefully monitor the regional and national capabilities available to both the decentralised facilities and centralised EU-IBISBA core services, and differentiate between aspirational services and operational ones.

Projects using EOSC Portal Services

A number of EOSC projects are demonstrating the use and value of the EOSC e-Infrastructure “portal” services for domain specific areas, outside of or affiliated with the ESFRIs. Ongoing EOSC-related projects general focus on:

- establishing EOSC services, onboarding services into the EOSC and transnational access to national resources
- the development, adoption and dissemination of the FAIR principles for data.

The following are of note for EU-IBISBA as they relate to digital technologies that EU-IBISBA is adopting or are related to the bioscience sector.

[EOSC-Pillar¹³⁵](https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/) is planning a FAIR Federated Data Space based on GO-FAIR FAIR DataPoints and use cases including *exploring reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community*. This aims to explore the possible interactions between already available Galaxy computing services and data repositories, in order to build an integrated and interoperable service for ELIXIR and the wider Life Science user community as a whole. *Galaxy is the workflow platform IBISBA1.o’s SynBioCAD workflows service.*

[EOSC-Synergy¹³⁶](https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/) cites the use of biomedical services using the EOSC Marketplace: [OpenEBench¹³⁷](https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/thematic-services/openebench/), the ELIXIR benchmarking and technical monitoring platform for bioinformatics tools, web servers and workflows which uses ELIXIR AAI, EOSC-Life Services such as WorkflowHub and is planning work on EUDAT; [UMSA – Untargeted Mass-Spectrometry Analysis¹³⁸](https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/thematic-services/umsa/) service from the EIRENE ESFRI which uses Galaxy workflows, ELIXIR AAI and some computing resources that are not clear how they are EOSC; and [SCIPION¹³⁹](https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/thematic-services/scipion/) a plugin-based workflow management system. EOSC-Synergy is planning to make extensive use of the EGI and EUDAT service offerings, so it will be interesting to monitor progress in practice.

¹³⁵ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>

¹³⁶ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

¹³⁷ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/thematic-services/openebench/>

¹³⁸ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/thematic-services/umsa/>

¹³⁹ <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/thematic-services/scipion/>

[RELIANCE¹⁴⁰](https://www.reliance-project.eu/) seeks to extend the EOSC's capabilities with an enhanced support for various research activities, aligned with the EOSC Interoperability Framework FAIR Digital Objects. Its focus is advanced geospatial data management and text mining for Copernicus data, using Research Objects [RO-Crate¹⁴¹](https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/) to manage data throughout its lifecycle.

3.2 *Thematic Research Infrastructures*

The [European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures¹⁴²](https://www.esfri.eu/) (ESFRI) aims to transform the availability of state-of-the-art facilities for researchers by making common investments easier at regional, national and European levels for the benefit of the ERA. European RIs are intended to “foster the definition, implementation and further development of advanced solutions for the effective provisioning and use of high-quality scientific data, with effective metadata descriptors, ease of access, interoperability and reusability, fully implementing the FAIR principles”. EU-IBISBA was placed on the ESFRI roadmap in 2018, and PREP-IBISBA is its preparatory funding project. Over 50 ESFRIs have been established; 14 in the BioMedical Sciences.

To better support coherence across the research ecosystem, ESFRI Landmarks and Projects are expected to lead by example and develop clear data policies, guidance on policy harmonisation and provide guidance on how to make emerging and/or enhanced policies more visible via RI websites and through registries such as FAIRsharing.

One of the European Commission's drivers for linking RIs and EOSC is a need for storing, transferring and analysing large amounts of data, and for combining data and observations from several sources, reducing barriers between research disciplines. The drive for collaborating on common underlying resources, the development of interoperability concepts for effective data sharing, and the universal cataloging of data across disciplines informs much of EC ESFRI-EOSC policy and its implementation projects. The EC's vision of EOSC is to provide a chance to increase data sharing beyond RIs, by providing European researchers with “seamless access to data and value-added services from different national and regional backgrounds”.

The e-Infrastructure projects (funded by EC DG-CONNECT) and the thematic ESFRIs (funded by the EC Research and Innovation) come from different cultures and have different agendas. In principle, the services developed over 15 years by the e-Infrastructure projects (openAIRE, FREYA, EGI, EUDAT, GEANT, PRACE) should provide services that are fit for and convenient for their users, represented in the ESFRIs. However, this isn't always the case. There is a long-held suspicion by the RIs that the e-Infrastructures are independently operating, and seek to serve European Commission perspectives rather than users, and that they are limited to only some user communities, taking little heed of ease of user adoption and not being required to do so. The RIs use their own or the open/commercial services already in the workflows of their researchers.

¹⁴⁰ <https://www.reliance-project.eu/>

¹⁴¹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹⁴² <https://www.esfri.eu/>

To bridge these communities the five thematic ESFRI Cluster projects have been established to link Research Infrastructures to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹⁴³:

- [ESCAPE¹⁴⁴](#) - European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures
- [EOSC-Life¹⁴⁵](#) - Providing an open collaborative space for digital biology in Europe
- [SSHOC¹⁴⁶](#) - Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
- [ENVRI-FAIR¹⁴⁷](#) - ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES BUILDING FAIR SERVICES ACCESSIBLE FOR SOCIETY, INNOVATION AND RESEARCH
- [PaNOSC¹⁴⁸](#) - Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud

Other thematic projects include EXPANDS launched in 2019 and Thematic Clouds launched in 2019 and 2020 in the sectors of transport, food, marine, health and earth-observation. The EOSC-Future project has EOSC Core e-Infrastructure services and ESFRI partners, and made a call for researchers and actors from all scientific fields to closely support the co-design of EOSC through a user group.

Various meetings and consultations have taken place to build bridges and incorporate the RIs into EOSC including:

- ESFRI RIs-EOSC workshops "Research Infrastructures shaping EOSC" undertaken in partnership with the [StR-ESFRI₂ Project¹⁴⁹](#). PREP-IBISBA attended the second of these on [6 & 7 October 2020¹⁵⁰](#).
- The ESFRI cluster projects [position on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC¹⁵¹](#) in 2020¹⁵²

Many of the current Cluster projects are developing and delivering training as part of their project activity which could help to increase overall EOSC readiness amongst communities of practice. The aim of the Cluster projects is to implement interfaces to "integrate computer and data management solutions, to create cross-border and open cooperation spaces and to promote clouds via the EOSC Portal for a larger user community"¹⁵³. This operates at two levels:

- **Federation within the Clusters of the RIs**, their resources, infrastructures and policies against common standards and cross-cataloguing, and shared e-Infrastructure following the FAIR principles and against concrete use cases;

¹⁴³ Five new ESFRI cluster projects in the EOSC panorama. (21 April, 2020). <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/news/five-new-esfri-clusterprojects-eosc-panorama>

¹⁴⁴ <https://projectescape.eu/>

¹⁴⁵ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

¹⁴⁶ <https://sshopencloud.eu/>

¹⁴⁷ <https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/>

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.panosc.eu/>

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.esfri.eu/str-esfri>

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-events/2nd-esfri-ris-eosc-workshop-research-infrastructures-shaping-eosc?qt-event=1#qt-event>

¹⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675081>

¹⁵² Gotz, Andy, Petzold, Andreas, Asmi, Ari, Blomberg, Niklas, Lamanna, Giovanni, & Dekker, Ron. (2020). ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675081>

¹⁵³ https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/White_paper_ESFRI-final.pdf

- **Integration of the RIs** with the e-Infrastructure services and tools offered by the cross cutting EOSC services.

The simplified view is that RIs provide “vertical thematic” services (e.g. data services, research products services, catalogues, workflow management systems) and the EOSC provider offer “horizontal e-infrastructure” services (e.g. AAI, data storage, cloud compute, networking, cataloguing). As Figure 4 presented, the EOSC vision is to combine thematic RI and generic e-Infrastructure services, and to identify and share common services across the thematic RIs. In practice the Clusters operate at varying levels of coupling between the RIs within the Clusters depending on the heterogeneity of the RIs, and with the EOSC services depending on the added value of EOSC services for the RIs end-users against the cost of adoption. Moreover, the Cluster projects are not only users of services provided by EOSC but also provides e-Infrastructure services themselves, often tailored to their disciplines needs. The boundary between thematic service and e-Infrastructure service is not always so distinct.

The short summary is that the EOSC services as developed by the EOSC Core projects need to be more convenient for ESFRIs and their users to use, and the EOSC core projects need to engage more to serve the needs of the ESFRI users. The ESFRI thematic cluster view on EOSC is summarised in figure 8, where EOSC stands for **E**-infrastructure **C**onsolidation + **O**pen **S**cience and **S**cientific **C**ommunities’ content and users. This put the ESFRIs’ firmly at the centre of EOSC’s construction rather than a “user” on the edge of EOSC.

Figure 8: ESFRI thematic cluster view on EOSC, from¹⁵⁴

¹⁵⁴ Blomberg, Niklas, & Petzold, Andreas. (2020). ESFRI thematic cluster view on EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3631247>

EOSC-Life Cluster

[EOSC-Life¹⁵⁵](#), launched in 2019, brings together the 13 Life Science 'ESFRI' research infrastructures to create an open, digital and collaborative space for biological and medical research using Cloud technologies (figure 9). It has four main pillars:

- **cross-RI Data Commons** - "cloudification" of data repositories, registries and data services to publish 'FAIR' data and a catalogue of services provided by participating RIs for the management, storage and reuse of data in the EOSC.
- **cross RI Method Commons** - implement workflows that cross disciplines and address the needs of interdisciplinary science, building a portable "Tool and Workflow Collaboratory" of open services supporting the execution of many workflow management systems over data on premise or in the cloud
- **Trusted Research Commons** - address the data policies needed for human research data under GDPR with interoperable provenance information to describe the history of the sample and data to ensure reproducibility and adherence to regulatory requirements.
- Support the development and management of data and workflows pertinent to **COVID-19**, including the [EC COVID-19 Data Platform](#).¹⁵⁶

Figure 9: The Technical Goals of EOSC-Life

Services, policies, methodologies and resources developed or managed by the participating RIs and co-developed for the Cluster are of particular interest to EU-IBISBA and in some cases are already being used by IBISBAHub from IBISBA1.0. The RIs interesting or relevant to EU-IBISBA are in Table 3 - they either provide services that can be reused or share/coordinate facilities. EOSC-Life is a short term project. The thematic RIs are also members of a long term organisation [Life Science Research](#)¹⁵⁷ Infrastructures that EU-IBISBA has recently joined.

ELIXIR¹⁵⁸	unites 23 countries and 220+ life science organisations managing life science data from capture to analysis. Coordinates, integrates and sustains bioinformatics resources across its member states and enables users in
--------------------------------------	--

¹⁵⁵ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

¹⁵⁶ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/the-european-covid-19-data-platform>

¹⁵⁷ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>

¹⁵⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

	<p>academia and industry to access services.</p> <p>ELIXIR is important to all the RIs as its chief role is data infrastructure for all of Life Sciences. ELIXIR coordinates EOSC-Life. See below for more details.</p>
<p>ISBE¹⁵⁹ Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe</p>	<p>aimed to connect national systems biology centres. Adopted the FAIRDOM-SEEK¹⁶⁰ as its cataloguing/repository platform and the FAIRDOMHub¹⁶¹, a public open resource hosted in Germany.</p> <p>EU-IBISBA, uses the same platform and has established IBISBAHub¹⁶².</p> <p>ISBE is now off the ESFRI roadmap and will be rolled into ELIXIR.</p>
<p>EMBRC¹⁶³ European Marine Biological Research Centre</p>	<p>provides access to marine resources, services and facilities that allow researchers, from both academia and industry, to study the ocean and develop innovative solutions to tackle societal issues.</p> <p>provides a primitive single service catalogue¹⁶⁴ which is just a list of resources and email contact addresses.</p>
<p>EURO-BIOIMAGING¹⁶⁵</p>	<p>focuses on biological and biomedical imaging, allowing life scientists to access imaging instruments, expertise, training opportunities and data management services. Specialist data repositories.</p>
<p>MIRRI¹⁶⁶ Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure</p>	<p>focuses on microbial biodiversity to exploit knowledge to further bioeconomy and bioscience. over 50 public biorepositories and research institutes and provides a web search interface to access many of its resources, including the search for microbial strains, yeast strains and glossary terms. Provides a single service catalogue¹⁶⁷ which is even more primitive than EMBRC.</p>

Table 3: Life Science RIs interesting or relevant to EU-IBISBA

ELIXIR is the very well-established RI for Life Science data¹⁶⁸. Fundamentally, ELIXIR is connecting 23 national bioinformatic networks, known within ELIXIR as Nodes¹⁶⁹, coordinated by a Hub. Some ELIXIR Nodes predate ELIXIR, such as EMBL-EBI and the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, many are new. ELIXIR facilitates collaboration between its member institutes and researchers with organizational groupings:

- [Platforms¹⁷⁰](#): Data, Tools, Interoperability (aka FAIR Data Services), Training and Compute, with access to ELIXIR funding

¹⁵⁹ <https://project.isbe.eu/>

¹⁶⁰ <https://fair-dom.org/platform/seek/>

¹⁶¹ <https://fairdomhub.org/>

¹⁶² <https://hub.ibisba.eu/>

¹⁶³ <https://www.embrc.eu/>

¹⁶⁴ <https://www.embrc.eu/services/service-catalogue>

¹⁶⁵ <https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/>

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.mirri.org/>

¹⁶⁷ <https://www.mirri.org/mirri-services/>

¹⁶⁸ Jennifer Harrow, Rachel Drysdale, Andrew Smith, Susanna Repo, Jerry Lanfear, Niklas Blomberg, ELIXIR: providing a sustainable infrastructure for life science data at European scale, *Bioinformatics*, 2021, btab481, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btab481>

¹⁶⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/nodes>

¹⁷⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms>

- [Communities](#)¹⁷¹, that identify the needs of domain or technology-specific research around a specific theme - currently total of 12, with access to ELIXIR funding, including: [Galaxy Workflows](#)¹⁷², [Microbial Biotechnology](#)¹⁷³, and [Metabolomics](#)¹⁷⁴. *Microbial Biotechnology is co-lead by members of EU-IBISBA.*
- [Focus groups](#)¹⁷⁵, that are agile structures that bring interested parties together around a particular topic, without access to ELIXIR funding - currently 12 including: [EOSC](#)¹⁷⁶, [FAIR Training](#)¹⁷⁷, [Impact](#)¹⁷⁸, [Innovation and Industry](#)¹⁷⁹, [Machine Learning \(AI\)](#)¹⁸⁰, [Registries](#)¹⁸¹, [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\) Activities](#)¹⁸² and [Systems Biology](#)¹⁸³. *Systems Biology has representation from EU-IBISBA members.*

As part of joining ELIXIR, each Node contributes a set of services¹⁸⁴ that are aligned with the Platforms, and other services and activities are born of Node collaborations or from work on EU projects awarded to ELIXIR. Table 4 lists some of the services that will be of value to EU-IBISBA.

EU-IBISBA already has a close relationship with ELIXIR through common membership of the University of Manchester, common infrastructure and shared resources. EU-IBISBA should consider a more formal arrangement.

FAIR Data Services, Resources and Activities	
http://identifiers.org/ ¹⁸⁵	Identifiers Resolution service, provides re-usable identifiers for any data used in the biomedical sciences, which allows the data to “live on” should the provider change, move, or cease support. Many biological databases therefore choose to use identifiers.org for their “official” URIs - for example, Reactome. For database providers, this route can be an easy and maintenance-free way of providing persistent URIs for your data. <i>IBISBAHub can use identifiers.org for URIs to database entries in community public archives.</i>
http://fairsharing.org/ ¹⁸⁶	Registry of standards, repositories and data policies and how they interlink. Serves all disciplines and has been adopted by funders, publishers, RDA and other organisations. A technical refresh in Summer 2021 has new APIs. Integrated into the ELIXIR RDMkit and FAIRAssist, a decision-making tool for choosing deposition databases, and the ELIXIR Data Stewardship Wizard.

¹⁷¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities>

¹⁷² <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/galaxy>

¹⁷³ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/microbial-biotechnology>

¹⁷⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/metabolomics>

¹⁷⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups>

¹⁷⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/eosc>

¹⁷⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/fair-training>

¹⁷⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/impact>

¹⁷⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/innovation-and-industry>

¹⁸⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/machine-learning>

¹⁸¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/registries>

¹⁸² <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/rda-activities>

¹⁸³ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/systems-biology>

¹⁸⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/services>

¹⁸⁵ <http://identifiers.org/>

¹⁸⁶ <http://fairsharing.org/>

	<i>IBISBAHub should be registered and we should make use of the FAIRsharing collections for standards and deposition databases for EU-IBISBA projects</i>
FAIRassist	The FAIRassist tool, part of the FAIRsharing resource, is under development to offer personalised guidance to discover resources, such as data and metadata standards and databases, which should be used to make data FAIR.
RDMkit ¹⁸⁷	The ELIXIR Research Data Management toolkit written by life scientists for life scientists to guide FAIR data management throughout the data lifecycle. The contents are generated and maintained by the ELIXIR community and beyond. Links into content in FAIRsharing, TeSS, Bio.tools, and will be integrated with DSW, FAIRCookbook and WorkflowHub to create a one-stop shop for knowledge about FAIR Data in the Life Sciences. Pages on “Tools Assemblies” including FAIRDOME-SEEK examples. Sponsored by the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. <i>PREP-IBISBA staff already contribute to RDMkit. Pages on Microbial Biotechnology and a very rich resource for IBISBA projects and training. IBISBA pages for Tools Assemblies based on the e-Infrastructure framework proposed in Del 8.2.</i>
http://bioschemas.org/ ¹⁸⁸	Opinionated profiles and types for Schema.org markup, and when used info websites indexable by search engines and other services. Encourages consistent use of structured information making it easier to discover, collate, and analyse distributed resources. A key metadata component of the ELIXIR Tools ecosystem and EOSC-Life Workflow collaboratory as well as used by other registries and repositories in ELIXIR. Work is ongoing in EOSC-Enhance to harvest Bioschemas into the OpenAIRE Research Graph. <i>PREP-IBISBA are leading areas of Bioschema and lead the development of the Computational Workflow profile, used by WorkflowHub. IBISBAHub should use Bioschemas markup, not just for workflows but all its content types.</i>
Ontology Lookup Service (OLS) ¹⁸⁹	A repository for biomedical ontologies that aims to provide a single point of access to the latest ontology versions, accessible programmatically via the OLS API. Not as comprehensive as BioPortal but more highly curated. <i>IBISBAHub and associated tools (e.g. Rightfield) may use this for ontology terms.</i>
Ontology Mapping Service ¹⁹⁰ (OxO)	A service for finding mappings (or cross-references) between terms from ontologies, vocabularies and coding standards. OxO imports mappings from a variety of sources including the Ontology Lookup Service and a subset of mappings provided by the UMLS . <i>IBISBAHub and associated tools (e.g. Rightfield) may use this for cross referencing ontology terms.</i>
BridgeDB ¹⁹¹	A framework to map identifiers between various biological databases. These mappings are provided for genes, proteins, genetic variants, metabolites, and metabolic reactions. BridgeDb includes a Java library that provides an API for programmatic access.
FAIRDOME-SEEK ¹⁹²	A mature web-based resource for organising, sharing and publishing heterogeneous scientific research datasets, models or simulations, protocols, workflows, samples,

¹⁸⁷ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

¹⁸⁸ <http://bioschemas.org/>

¹⁸⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/>

¹⁹⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/spot/oxo/>

¹⁹¹ <https://bridgedb.github.io/>

¹⁹² <http://fairdom-seek.org/>

	<p>publications and other research outcomes. The platform enables the building of Project Hubs where investigators can store, share, access, connect and interact with digital objects generated from their research, and use them in their own analyses. Used by several ELIXIR Nodes (UK, DE, BE, NL, NO) and examples of its use in RDMkit tool assemblies. A customised version of the platform implements the EOSC-Life WorkflowHub.</p> <p><i>IBISBAHub is a customised version of FAIRDOME-SEEK. Extensions and how the IBISBAHub is used should be contributed to ELIXIR and EOSC</i></p>
FAIR Cookbook ¹⁹³	<p>an online resource for the Life Sciences with recipes that help you to make and keep data FAIR. Unlike RDMkit, more appropriate for expert data stewardship, platform developers and retrospective FAIRification of legacy datasets. Sponsored by the FAIRplus project.</p>
Data Stewardship Wizard ¹⁹⁴	<p>A powerful decision support tool for creating Smart Data Management Plans. Data Stewards capture and combine their knowledge and expertise with respect to the specific needs of a domain or an organisation. Researchers are truly guided through composing a DMP which can be then exported using selected template and format, including machine-actionable. Complements the RDMkit and these are being combined. Uses entries in FAIRsharing.</p> <p><i>IBISBAHub can develop customized DMPs using DSW combined with IBISBA appropriate content in FAIRsharing.</i></p>
OmicsDI ¹⁹⁵	<p>Provides a knowledge discovery framework across heterogeneous omics data (genomics, proteomics, transcriptomics and metabolomics).</p>
<p>Trusted Data Repositories</p> <p>Data repositories that Nodes operate as public and reference archives. <i>ELIXIR has recently started work on "data brokering" pipelines - that is moving data from project resources such as IBISBAHub to ELIXIR public archives. IBISBAHub can reference entries in these TDRs.</i></p>	
Deposition Databases ¹⁹⁶	<p>ELIXIR has compiled a list of resources that it recommends for the deposition of experimental data. 12 are listed, including MetaboLights¹⁹⁷, IntAct¹⁹⁸, BioSamples¹⁹⁹, and BioModels²⁰⁰.</p>
Core Data Resources ²⁰¹	<p>Selected through review for sustainability support and extra developments. 23 currently listed, including Reactome²⁰². These CDRs are part of ELIXIR's sustainability effort in the Global Biodata Coalition²⁰³.</p>
Node Data Resources ²⁰⁴	<p>Nodes also support other additional data resources</p>

¹⁹³ <https://fairplus.github.io/the-fair-cookbook/content/home.html>

¹⁹⁴ <https://ds-wizard.org/>

¹⁹⁵ <https://www.omicsdi.org/>

¹⁹⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

¹⁹⁷ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

¹⁹⁸ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/intact/>

¹⁹⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>

²⁰⁰ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/biomodels/>

²⁰¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/core-data-resources>

²⁰² <https://reactome.org/>

²⁰³ <https://globalbiodata.org/>

²⁰⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/services/>

Tools, Analysis and Computational Services ELIXIR is developing a Tools Platform EcoSystem with an integrating metadata framework and using GA4GH ²⁰⁵ APIs.	
Galaxy Workflow System and Analysis platform ²⁰⁶	Galaxy is an open, web-based platform for data-intensive computational research that spans beyond the life sciences. It allows researchers without programming experience to run analysis workflows on their data, share their results, and enable others to repeat the same analyses. Galaxy makes science reproducible, facilitates sharing of data and results, and removes the hassle of installing software tools from users. Galaxy Europe ²⁰⁷ is a public Galaxy service operated by ELIXIR nodes. <i>IBISBA1.o's computational workflow platform Galaxy-SynBioCAD is a Galaxy instance. EU-IBISBA should consider partnering with Galaxy Europe to provide a sustained workflow service.</i>
Bio.tools ²⁰⁸	A registry of software tools, databases and services for bioinformatics and the life sciences, marked up with Bioschemas and EDAM terms. <i>EU-IBISBA tools must be registered and a useful source for tools. EU-IBISBA should make a bio.tools collection.</i>
Biocontainers ²⁰⁹	A registry of software you can run on any operating system in containers.
WorkflowHub ²¹⁰	A registry of computational workflows that supports workflows of any kind from any system, including Jupyter Notebooks, CWL and Galaxy. Supports RO-Crate and is sponsored by the EOSC-Life project. Implements GA4GH APIs for seamless Galaxy execution with Galaxy Europe. Based on FAIRDOM-SEEK. Workflows are marked up using Bioschemas and EDAM. <i>PREP-IBISBA already registers its workflows on WorkflowHub in a curated collection²¹¹, referenced by IBISBAHub. A key part of the proposed IBISBA technical framework in Del 8.2; moving IBISBA's workflows to Galaxy Europe may make a smooth execution service.</i>
EDAM Ontology ²¹²	A comprehensive ontology of well-established, familiar concepts that are prevalent within computational biology, bioinformatics, and bioimage informatics ²¹³ . EDAM includes types of data and data identifiers, data formats, operations, and topics related to data analysis in life sciences. EDAM provides a set of concepts with preferred terms and synonyms, related terms, definitions, and other information. EDAM is particularly suitable for semantic annotations and categorisation of diverse resources related to bioscientific data analysis: e.g. tools, workflows, or training materials. EDAM is also useful in data management, for recording provenance metadata of processed bioscientific data. <i>EU-IBISBA should use EDAM</i>
RO-Crate ²¹⁴	A community effort to establish a lightweight approach to packaging research digital objects with their metadata. Based on schema.org annotations in JSON-LD, and aims to make best-practice in formal metadata description accessible and practical for use in

²⁰⁵ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

²⁰⁶ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

²⁰⁷ <https://galaxyproject.eu/>

²⁰⁸ <https://bio.tools/>

²⁰⁹ <https://biocontainers.pro/>

²¹⁰ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

²¹¹ <https://workflowhub.eu/projects/1>

²¹² <http://edamontology.org/>

²¹³ <https://github.com/edamontology/edam-bioimaging>

²¹⁴ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

	<p>a wider variety of situations, from an individual researcher working with a folder of data, to large data-intensive computational research environments. RO-Crate is used for reporting, service exchange, registry and repository deposition, import and export, archiving and citation. These are implementation mechanisms for EOSC FAIR Digital Objects, and for depositing objects into OpenAIRE and Zenodo. ELIXIR and EOSC-Life use Workflow-RO-Crates.</p> <p><i>The FAIRDOME-SEEK implements RO-Crate features so IBISBAHub should easily adopt this increasingly popular metadata exchange mechanism.</i></p>
ELIXIR-AAI²¹⁵	<p>Enables researchers to use their home organisation credentials or community or commercial identities (e.g. ORCID, LinkedIn) to sign in and access data and services they need. It also allows service providers (both in academia and industry) to control and manage access rights of their users and create different access levels for research groups or international projects.</p> <p>The Life Science Login is a AAI system from EOSC-Life. It will supersede the ELIXIR-AAI.</p> <p><i>The IBISBAHub already implements ELIXIR-AAI, as does the Galaxy workflow infrastructure also used by IBISBA1.0</i></p>
Common Workflow Language²¹⁶	<p>Although not an ELIXIR or EOSC-Life resource - it is an open community independent of ELIXIR - the CWL has been adopted as an open standard for describing analysis workflows and tools in a way that makes them portable and scalable across a variety of software and hardware environments, from workstations to cluster, cloud, and high-performance computing (HPC) environments. Galaxy is developing support for CWL descriptions.</p> <p><i>EU-IBISBA should adopt CWL for describing its computational workflows.</i></p>
Training	
TeSS²¹⁷	<p>ELIXIR's Training Portal for browsing, discovering and organising life sciences training resources, aggregated from ELIXIR nodes and 3rd-party providers. Content is harvested using Bioschema markup.</p> <p><i>EU-IBISBA should become a source for TeSS and contribute to TeSS materials, workflows and learning pathways.</i></p>
NPOS/ELIXIR Data Stewardship competency framework²¹⁸	<p>The Data Stewardship Competency Framework distinguishes three data steward roles (policy, research and infrastructure) and eight competence areas (policy/strategy, compliance, alignment with FAIR data principles, services, infrastructure, knowledge management, network, data archiving and transferable skills). For each of these three data stewardship role competencies, KSAs (knowledge, skills and abilities) and learning outcomes (including Bloom's level) are given.</p> <p><i>EU-IBISBA should adopt this competency framework.</i></p>

Table 4 ELIXIR Services and Activities of interest to IBISBA

EOSC-Life has funded "Demonstrator" projects, scientific and technical pilot projects that provide concrete scientific use-cases, to make data, tools and workflows available in the cloud for re-use by the scientific community. Further project calls enable dataset / service / data resource to become newly available in a cloud instance, and implement FAIR metrics.

²¹⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/services/compute/aaai>

²¹⁶ <https://www.commonwl.org/>

²¹⁷ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

²¹⁸ <https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/>

EOSC-Life reports its achievements²¹⁹ and makes a great deal of use of the ELIXIR services in Table 4, many of which are supported through the project. Table 5 lists further services IBISBA needs to monitor.

LS Login²²⁰	<p>The Life Science Login enables researchers to use their home organisation credentials or community or commercial identities (e.g. ORCID, LinkedIn) to sign in and access data and services they need across multiple platforms. It also allows service providers (both in academia and industry) to control and manage access rights of their users and create different access levels for research groups or international projects. Piloting has begun. This is to replace ELIXIR-AAI <i>EU-IBISBA should review whether to move to LS AAI.</i></p>
Terms4FAIRskills²²¹	<p>Terms4FAIRskills is a terminology for the skills, competencies and knowledge necessary to make data FAIR and to keep it FAIR. The terminology can be used to assist with the creation and assessment of stewardship curricula; to facilitate the annotation, discovery and evaluation of FAIR-enabling materials (e.g. training) and resources; and to enable the formalisation of job descriptions and CVs with recognised, structured competencies.</p>
Toolbox for sharing of sensitive data²²²	<p>A toolbox is currently under development, providing pooled information on recommendations, best practices, software tools etc. to researchers who wish to share and/or use sensitive data in a cloud environment in general, and EOSC in particular. The sensitivity of the data may arise from its personal nature but can also be related to intellectual property considerations, biohazard concerns, or the Nagoya Protocol.</p>
Provenance standard for life science data²²³	<p>A provenance model is being developed and its instance is being standardised under ISO 23494 to describe the history of data in life sciences in distributed environments, in order to assess reusability of data for further research and to improve reproducibility of research results. The model aims at documenting the full chain of history of data all the way to its source (biological entity), supporting documenting history of sensitive data (such as genetic or clinical data) and is designed to implement interlinking across institutional boundaries. The standard also supports compliance with the Nagoya Protocol.</p>
<p>Tool and Workflow Collaboratory</p>	<p>A cloud-based workflow collaboratory to drive implementation of FAIR workflows across disciplines and RI boundaries, and foster tool-focused collaborations and reuse between communities via the sharing, reuse and repurposing of data analysis workflows. The collaboratory aims to provide a framework for researchers and workflow specialists to use and reuse workflows; implements services and a metadata framework based on RO-Crate, Bioschemas, CWL and GA4GH APIs. Figure 10 shows the architecture of the framework. <i>EU-IBISBA should use and contribute to this Collaboratory, and is already doing so, leading development of the Bioschemas profiles and using RO-Crate, Galaxy and WorkflowHub.</i></p>

Table 5 EOSC-Life Services and Activities of interest to IBISBA

²¹⁹ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/eosc-life-achievements-brochure-Final.pdf>

²²⁰ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/l5-login.html>

²²¹ <https://terms4fairskills.github.io/>

²²² <https://zenodo.org/record/4483694#.YRKLPUDTXZQ>

²²³ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/ISO-23494.pdf>

Figure 10: The EOSC-Life Tool and Workflow Collaboratory

4 Conclusion

This deliverable reviews the EU e-Infrastructure landscape, focusing in particular on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), associated projects and the Life Science thematic Research Infrastructures. EU-IBISBA should use the e-infrastructure services available across EU countries and beyond where appropriate, and contribute to the EU e-Infrastructure landscape overall as part of the EOSC.

EU-IBISBA should seek to become an EOSC Association Member as soon as it has its legal entity status. The development of the Minimal Viable EOSC and its services will be considered in the technical digital framework for EU-IBISBA reported in Deliverable 8.2.

A large number of services and activities developed in the EOSC-Life RI cluster and the ELIXIR RI have been identified as relevant to EU-IBISBA and in several cases PREP-IBISBA has already adopted and contributed to shared services and standards.

5 Partners involved in the work

UNIMAN: Carole Goble, Alan Williams, Munazah Andrabi

WUR: Jasper Koehorst

6 Annexes

6.1 Annexe A: Meetings attended

- ESFRI RIs-EOSC "Research Infrastructures shaping EOSC" workshops 06/10/2020-07/10/2020
- RDA-GEDE Workshop on FAIR Digital Objects 14/04/2020
- RDA/openAIRE virtual workshop 06/05/2020

- EOSC Webinar: Establishing open & FAIR Research Data 19/05/2020
- ECCB FAIR Computational Workflows Workshop, 02/09/2020
- FAIRsFAIR workshop on Metadata catalogue integration for interdisciplinary research, 11/09/2020
- GMDS workshop FAIR Data Infrastructures, 15/10/2020
- CODATA DDI-CDI Webinar 20/11/2020
- FAIR Convergence Symposium, 27/11/2020 - 04/12/2020
- WorkflowsRI workshop, 13/01/2021
- FAIR Digital Object forum CWRP and Galaxy workshop, 11/03/2021
- CODATA FAIRsFAIR catalogue integration 30/03/2021
- WorkflowsRI Summit 2, 07/04/2021
- AGU Data Citation Community of Practice Workshop, 08/04/2021
- RDA ESFRI House of Commons debate, debater on motion 1, 19/04/2021
- RDA Plenary 17 20/04/2021-22/04/2021
- USA NASEM workshop on changing the culture of data Management and sharing panel speaker, 28/04/2021-29/04/2021
- RDA/FDO Webinar RO-Crate: A framework for packaging research products into FAIR Research Objects 15/03/2021
- FAIRsFAIR FAIR Digital Object Forum FDO-Sem WG workshop 04/06/2021
- DataVerse User Community Conference 15/06/2021
- EOSC Symposium 2021 15/06/2021-18/06/2021
- FAIR Festival 21/06/2021-22/06/2021
- JOBIM2021, 08/07/2021
- GO-FAIR USA Webinar FAIR Computational Workflows 16/06/2021
- AGU Community of Practice for Data Citation WG 06/06/2021
- CS3 Community Conference 25-29/01/2021
- BOSC2021 29-30/07 2021

Regular Participation (bi-weekly/monthly)

- EOSC-Life WorkflowHub Club
- FAIRDOME-SEEK developers & FAIRDOME Club
- Bioschemas Community meeting
- RO-Crate Community meeting
- RDA - Data Fabric FAIR Digital Object IG

6.2 Annexe B: EOSC Projects

<p>STR-ESFRI²²⁴</p> <p><i>Support to Reinforce the European Strategy Forum on</i></p>	<p>Reinforces the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures providing additional resources, tools and expertise. It helps run the ESFRI Working Groups²²⁵, run workshops, write white papers and disseminate policy</p>
---	--

²²⁴ <https://www.esfri.eu/str-esfri>

²²⁵ <https://www.esfri.eu/working-groups>

<p><i>Research Infrastructures</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 March 2019</p> <p>Duration: 36 months</p> <p>5 partners</p>	
<p>EOSC-Enhance²²⁶</p> <p><i>Connecting Thematic Communities to Advance Open Science</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 Dec 2019</p> <p>Duration 24 months</p> <p>15 partners</p>	<p>The development and management of the EOSC-Portal and the onboarding of provider content.</p> <p>Although there have been efforts towards engaging with the ESFRI Clusters and other thematic projects it is largely dominated by the e-Infrastructure providers. User experience and use cases for users of the Portal are less well understood than the drive from the EC for a “marketplace” catalogue.</p>
<p>EOSC-Nordic²²⁷</p> <p><i>A new path to European research and innovation in Nordic and Baltic countries</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 July 2019</p> <p>Duration: 36 months</p> <p>24 partners from 8 member states</p>	<p>EOSC-Nordic aims to facilitate the coordination of open science initiatives within the Nordic and Baltic countries and exploit synergies to achieve greater harmonisation at policy and service provision across these countries, catalysing the Nordic and Baltic uptake of the EOSC. By working together to realise EOSC at the regional level, the countries aim to provide “Nordic Added Value” (Nordisk Nytte).</p>
<p>NI4OS-Europe²²⁸</p> <p><i>National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 Sept 2019</p> <p>Duration: 36 months</p> <p>22 partners from 15 countries</p>	<p>The NI4OS-Europe project intends to support the development of national Open Science Cloud schemes in 15 EU Member States and associated countries from South East Europe. It aims to design, analyse and categorise the national Open Science environment in these countries to create national Open Science Cloud structures to support general EOSC governance. The project also aims to instill the EOSC philosophy and FAIR principles for data and provide technical and policy support for on-boarding of service providers into EOSC, including generic services (compute, data storage, data management), thematic services, repositories and data sets.</p> <p>Useful results include: Provider landscape analysis and provider categorization</p>
<p>EOSC-Pillar²²⁹</p> <p><i>Coordination and Harmonisation of National</i></p>	<p>Gathers representatives of national initiatives for coordinating data infrastructures and services in Italy, France, Germany, Austria and Belgium to establish a federation model for open science services. National initiatives are</p>

²²⁶ <https://eosc-portal.eu/enhance>

²²⁷ <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/>

²²⁸ <https://ni4os.eu/>

²²⁹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/>

<p><i>Initiatives, Infrastructures and Data services in Central and Western Europe</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 July 2019</p> <p>Duration: 36 months</p> <p>18 partners from 5 member states</p>	<p>key to involve user communities and research infrastructures both as test-beds for solutions, but also in their very design and sustainable evolution. By federating national initiatives through common policies, FAIR services, shared standards, and technical choices, the project hopes to stimulate open data and open science services offered through the EOSC portal, and implement some of the main pieces of the EOSC jigsaw. Through the coordination of national initiatives, EOSC-Pillar hopes to support the gradual alignment of policy and practice among countries and compliance to EOSC standards.</p> <p>The project's work plan is built around selected user-driven pilots from 7 scientific domains that will show EOSC in action and provide valuable input to guide the roll out of services for other communities.</p>
<p>CS₃MESH₄EOSC²³⁰</p> <p><i>Integrated open-source system to boost collaboration in cloud storage services</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 Jan 2020</p> <p>Duration: 36 months</p> <p>13 partners from 10 Member States</p>	<p>CS₃MESH₄EOSC focuses on combining the disconnected and independently developed Cloud Services for Synchronization and Sharing (CS₃) deployed in the research and educational space into a ScienceMesh, which would provide an interoperable platform to easily sync & share, and deploy applications and software components within the CS₃ community²³¹.</p> <p>CS₃ services are typically deployed by e-infrastructure providers, NRENs (National Research & Education Networks) and major research institutions, and are in the daily workflows for users, including researchers, students, scientists and engineers. CS₃ Services include: Dropbox, Nextcloud, Owncloud, Powerfolder, Pydio, Seafiler, and Syncany.</p>
<p>EOSC-Synergy²³²</p> <p><i>European Open Science Cloud - Expanding Capacities by building Capabilities</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 Sept 2019</p> <p>Duration: 36 months</p> <p>17 partners from 8 member states</p>	<p>Aims to contribute to the EOSC implementation by expanding national e-infrastructures and building human capacities in EOSC. In practice this means more compute and storage available, more datasets and tools to expand avenues of research.</p> <p>EOSC-synergy fosters the uptake of the EOSC core functions and horizontal services at national level.</p>

²³⁰ <https://cs3mesh4eosc.eu/>

²³¹ <https://www.cs3community.org/>

²³² <https://www.eosc-synergy.eu/>

<p>EOSC-Future²³³</p> <p>Starting date: 1 April 2021</p> <p>Duration: 30 months</p> <p>36 partners</p>	<p>Integrate, consolidate, and connect e-infrastructures, research communities, and initiatives in Open Science to further develop the EOSC Portal, EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange of the European Open Science Cloud.</p> <p>Currently recruiting for the EOSC Future User Group</p>
<p>EGI-ACE: Advanced Computing for EOSC²³⁴</p> <p><i>Advanced computing platform for open and data-driven science</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 Jan 2021</p> <p>Duration: 30 months</p> <p>33 partners</p>	<p>Coordinated by the EGI Foundation with a mission to empower researchers from all disciplines to collaborate on data- and compute-intensive research through free-at-point-of-use services.</p> <p>EGI-ACE will deliver the EOSC Compute Platform and contribute to the EOSC Data Commons through a federation of cloud compute and storage facilities, PaaS services and data spaces with analytics tools and federated access services.</p> <p>Will provide more than 82 million CPU hours, 250 thousand GPU hours for data processing and analytics, and 45 PB/month for hosting and exploiting research data.</p>
<p>RELIANCE REsearch Lifecycle mAnagemeNt for Earth Science²³⁵ Communities and CopErnicus users in EOSC</p> <p><i>Extending the research-enabling capabilities of the European Open Science Cloud</i></p> <p>Starting date: 1 Jan 2021</p> <p>Duration: 24 months</p> <p>9 Partners</p>	<p>Seeks to extend the EOSC's capabilities with an enhanced support for various research activities, aligned with the EOSC Interoperability Framework. It will boost the discovery of and access to research data, including Copernicus data, improve the extraction of relevant information, and manage the research lifecycle via research objects while promoting FAIR and open science principles. By adopting a holistic research management approach, the project aims to enhance support for multidisciplinary research, particularly in Earth Science, improving European science as a whole.</p> <p><i>RELIANCE is implementing RO-Crate Research Objects, as is IBISBA.</i></p>

6.3 Annexe C: EOSC Services

<p>Compute</p>	
<p>EGI Federation https://www.egi.eu/federation/</p> <p>A federation of computing and storage resource providers united by a mission to support research and development. The</p>	<p>EGI resources are provided by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The EGI Federated data centres²³⁸ • The EGI Federated Cloud providers²³⁹

²³³ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

²³⁴ <https://wtwww.egi.eu/projects/egi-ace/>

²³⁵ <https://www.reliance-project.eu/>

²³⁸ <https://www.egi.eu/federation/data-centres/>

²³⁹ <https://www.egi.eu/federation/egi-federated-cloud/>

<p>federation is governed by the participants represented in the EGI Council²³⁶ and coordinated by the EGI Foundation²³⁷. Publicly funded and provides compute and storage resources to support research and innovation.</p>	<p>EGI-ACE²⁴⁰ (EGI Advanced Computing for EOSC), currently funds EGI Federation to deliver “the” EOSC Compute Platform and contribute to “the” EOSC Data Commons through a federation of cloud compute and storage facilities, PaaS services and data spaces with analytics tools and federated access services. <i>Several Life science projects are listed²⁴¹, all of which have close ties with the EGI federation. Services like Jupyter Notebook support²⁴² it is unclear what is actually available to be “ordered”²⁴³. IBISBA would need to apply for access and know in advance what its compute needs are.</i></p>
<p>Open Clouds for Research Environments https://www.ocre-project.eu/</p> <p>Brings together cloud providers, Earth Observation organisations and the research and education community, through ready-to-use service agreements and €9.5 million in adoption funding.</p>	<p>Runs a pan-European tender and established framework agreements with cloud service providers that meet the specific requirements of the research community, saving institutions the time-consuming and complex process of doing this themselves. <i>The OCRE Catalogue²⁴⁴ displays the compliant Cloud-based digital service providers who have been contracted to supply the European Research and Academic communities by means of the OCRE framework.</i></p>
<p>EuroHPC https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/</p> <p>is a joint initiative between the EU, European countries and private partners to develop a World Class Supercomputing Ecosystem in Europe</p>	<p>Procures and deploys pre-exascale and petascale supercomputers in the EU, to be made available to Europe’s private and public users, scientific and industrial users everywhere across Europe. Access through calls for proposals. <i>We do not anticipate IBISBA needing such resources - evidence from IBISBA1.0 suggests that HTC on premise or cloud will be sufficient.</i></p>
<p>The PRACE Research Infrastructure²⁴⁵</p>	<p>Provides access to distributed persistent pan-European world-class HPC computing and data management systems and services. The main “Tier-0” systems offered by PRACE Hosting Members can be found on the HPC Systems²⁴⁶ page. <i>We do not anticipate EU-IBISBA needing such resources - evidence from IBISBA1.0 suggests that HTC on premise or cloud will be sufficient.</i></p>
<p>Data Storage, Management and Transfer</p>	

²³⁶ <https://www.egi.eu/about/egi-council/>

²³⁷ <https://www.egi.eu/about/egi-foundation/>

²⁴⁰ <https://www.egi.eu/projects/egi-ace/>

²⁴¹ <https://www.egi.eu/use-cases/scientific-applications-tools/>

²⁴² <https://marketplace.egi.eu/applications-on-demand/74-notebooks-for-researchers.html>

²⁴³ When we tried to buy some time it failed with “This site can’t be reached, Check if there is a typo in marketplace.egi.eu module, DNS_PROBE_FINISHED_NXDOMAIN”. Not encouraging.

²⁴⁴ <https://www.ocre-project.eu/services/cloud-suppliers>

²⁴⁵ <https://prace-ri.eu/hpc-access/>

²⁴⁶ <https://prace-ri.eu/hpc-access/hpc-systems/>

<p>The EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure https://eudat.eu/eudat-cdi</p> <p>Data services are provided by a pool of (national) data storage and service providers.</p>	<p>The Service Catalogue²⁴⁷ lists 7 services: B2ACCESS²⁴⁸, B2DROP²⁴⁹, B2FIND²⁵⁰, B2HANDLE²⁵¹, B2SAFE²⁵², B2SHARE²⁵³, B2STAGE²⁵⁴.</p> <p>DICE,²⁵⁵ Data Infrastructure Capacity for EOSC, currently funds EUDAT services to provide “cutting-edge data management services and a significant amount of storage resources for the EOSC”.</p> <p><i>EU-IBISBA would need to apply for access and clearly see the value proposition of these services. Generally these services have been adopted by projects that are bound with EUDAT and not widely outside that “club”.</i></p>
<p>GAIA-X https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/</p> <p>GAIA-X is a project to design the next generation of a federated European data infrastructure that is efficient and competitive, secure and trustworthy federation of data infrastructure²⁵⁶ and service providers for Europe²⁵⁷, which is supported by representatives of business, science. Initiated by France and Germany. The GAIA-X AISBL established in 2020 to govern the infrastructure.</p>	<p>A federated data infrastructure. Each node of the infrastructure forms an independent unit and can be clearly identified and classified by the decentrally administered self-description. A software repository provides components that must or can be used by all providers, depending on their categorisation. The components can be provided interoperably across multiple nodes. The necessary interfaces, services and products should be harmonized by standards and be easily identified and used in a central repository for all participants. More than 500 organisations from various countries are already involved in GAIA-X, it is claimed.</p> <p><i>It is a struggle to see what this currently offers EU-IBISBA - it could be a generalist infrastructure as a kind of sister to ELIXIR.</i></p>
<p>Cloud Services for Synchronization and Sharing (CS3)²⁵⁸</p> <p>https://www.cs3community.org/</p> <p>Cloud Services for Synchronization and Sharing (CS3) are typically deployed by e-infrastructure providers, NRENs (National Research & Education Networks) and major research institutions, and are in the</p>	<p>The CS3MESH4EOSC²⁵⁹ project bridges CS3 with EOSC, focusing on the federated aspects of infrastructure, rather than taking a centralised view, and recognises the pre-existence of local regional and commercial CS3 infrastructures.</p> <p>The project aims to build a ScienceMesh global collaboration service for researchers, educators, data curators and analysts based on Open Cloud Mesh²⁶⁰ and vendor-neutral CS3 APIs. An initial definition of the Science Mesh Protocols and APIs has been announced. ScienceMesh would allow users to retain control over</p>

²⁴⁷ <https://eudat.eu/catalogue>

²⁴⁸ <https://eudat.eu/services/b2access>

²⁴⁹ <https://eudat.eu/services/b2drop>

²⁵⁰ <https://eudat.eu/services/b2find>

²⁵¹ <https://eudat.eu/services/b2handle>

²⁵² <https://eudat.eu/services/b2safe>

²⁵³ <https://eudat.eu/services/b2share>

²⁵⁴ <https://eudat.eu/services/b2stage>

²⁵⁵ <https://www.dice-eosc.eu/>

²⁵⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_infrastructure

²⁵⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Europe>

²⁵⁸ <https://www.cs3community.org/>

²⁵⁹ <https://cs3mesh4eosc.eu/>

²⁶⁰ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/OCM/Open+Cloud+Mesh>

<p>daily workflows for users, including researchers, students, scientists and engineers.</p> <p>CS₃ Services include: Dropbox, GoogleDocs, Nextcloud, Owncloud, Powerfolder, Pydio, Seafiler, and Syncany. They are widely used in practice and are a key mechanism for moving data between services. Developing vendor-neutral CS₃ APIs.</p>	<p>their remote or domestic datasets, while at the same time becoming FAIR compatible and integrated with the EOSC²⁶¹. This becomes a platform to share & deploy application and software components, while providing rich collaborative workflows. Users would be able to directly access the service provided by the ScienceMesh from interfaces and discover the different functionalities. These services would be cross-cutting and discipline independent, and the ScienceMesh would support discipline specific application plugins or enable set ups of federations in discipline specific scope to develop their specific activities on top of them.</p> <p><i>The reality for EU-IBISBA is that much of the data will be held in house and within local data infrastructures using CS₃ services. RO-Crate is being proposed to be incorporated into the Mesh and into Zenodo through this project. This makes it very attractive to implement CS₃ services with FAIRDOME-SEEK, which is the software platform that IBISBAHub is built on. IBISBA attended the CS₃ community workshop January 2021²⁶², and is monitoring the project. CS₃MESH4EOSC is a small project but a growing community with a promising practical approach.</i></p>
<p>iRODS</p> <p>https://irods.org/</p>	<p>Open Source Data Management Software released as a production-level distribution. It virtualizes data storage resources, so users can take control of their data, regardless of where and on what device the data is stored.</p> <p>iRODS is an open community offering rather than a specific EOSC service. However it underpins a range of European data services including EUDAT and is widely used.</p> <p><i>iRODS is a potential service for EU-IBISBA general data storage.</i></p>
<p>Sharing and discovery: General Repositories, Registries & Catalogues</p>	
<p>Zenodo and InvenioRDM https://about.zenodo.org/ https://inveniosoftware.org/</p> <p>Zenodo was established in 2013 by OpenAIRE and CERN as a catch-all generalist repository for EC funded research. CERN provides the capability. Invenio²⁶³ is an open source project initially developed by CERN.</p>	<p>Zenodo is a European bedrock of open access and open data: DOI citable published objects and a sustained archive for FDOs and RO-Crates.</p> <p>Invenio is a suite of products.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● InvenioRDM²⁶⁴ - a repository/document management platform ● InvenioILS - an integrated library system ● Invenio Framework - a code library to build large-scale information systems such as InvenioRDM and InvenioILS

²⁶¹ <https://cs3.trust-it-services.dev/contribution-eosc-fair>

²⁶² <http://www.cs3community.org/2021/>

²⁶³ <https://inveniosoftware.org/about/>

²⁶⁴ <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/>

	<p>A number of EOSC projects (CS3MESH4EOSC²⁶⁵, RELIANCE) are adding RO-Crate capability into Zenodo; and the new lead of InvenioRDM has expressed a desire to add RO-Crate there too.</p> <p><i>Excellent resources to exploit in EU-IBISBA.</i></p>
<p>DataVerse https://dataverse.org/</p>	<p>Open source research data repository software to share, preserve, cite, explore, and analyze research data. A Dataverse repository is the software installation, which then hosts multiple virtual archives called Dataverse collections. Each Dataverse collection contains datasets, and each dataset contains descriptive metadata and data files (including documentation and code that accompany the data). As an organizing method, Dataverse collections may also contain other Dataverse collections. The central insight behind the Dataverse Project is to automate much of the job of the professional archivist, and to provide services for and to distribute credit to the data creator.</p> <p>DataVerse is an open community offering rather than a specific EOSC service. However it underpins a range of European data services and is widely used at the institutional and regional level, for example in Norway and the Netherlands.</p> <p><i>DataVerse is implementing RO-Crate capability. This makes it compatible with the EU-IBISBA digital infrastructure.</i></p>
<p>OpenAIRE https://www.openaire.eu/</p> <p>OpenAIRE is a legal entity It has Open Science experts in HEIs, data centres, and infrastructure consortia (so called NOADs) who give regular training and advice at national level about all aspects of Open Science.</p> <p>Funding: EOSC Future²⁶⁶ EOSC OpenAIRE-Nexus²⁶⁷ EOSC Enhance²⁶⁸</p>	<p>OpenAIRE is a world-wide CRIS (Current research information system) and a pillar of EOSC e-infrastructure services²⁶⁹. It serves funders/projects/organizations/authors and supports the aggregation of research products (pubs, datasets, software) from community repositories.</p> <p>Resource metadata maps onto OpenAIRE guidelines (standard application profiles) and additional services "enrich" and "improve" content, including a Research Graph²⁷⁰. It offers community dashboards²⁷¹ and monitoring dashboards²⁷², and feeds these to the EC.</p> <p>As EOSC Enhance project members they are working on common metadata and cross-catalogue metadata management with the EOSC Portal, and are working with ELIXIR on using Bioschema and RO-Crate to harvest their registries into OpenAIRE.</p> <p><i>IBISBAHub could be a feed service for OpenAIRE through its Bioschemas and RO-Crate support. The OpenAIRE Research Graph could be a useful resource to enrich the Hub. EU-IBISBA should review the benefits of an OpenAIRE community dashboard to monitor our ESFRI's impact.</i></p> <p><i>Our main issue is that OpenAIRE is about open research, and most of the Hub content is not expected to be open.</i></p>

²⁶⁵ <https://cs3mesh4eosc.eu/>

²⁶⁶ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

²⁶⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-nexus-project>

²⁶⁸ <https://eosc-portal.eu/enhance>

²⁶⁹ <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-and-eosc>

²⁷⁰ <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

²⁷¹ <https://connect.openaire.eu/>

²⁷² <https://monitor.openaire.eu/>

<p>B2FIND</p> <p>https://eudat.eu/services/b2find</p> <p>Offered by EUDAT</p>	<p>A dataset discovery service harvesting and aggregating exclusively metadata about research datasets. 1,338,169 datasets, 28,458 datasets in Life Sciences typically deposited in Institutional repositories Datasets are contributed by communities, including INRAE²⁷³. B2FIND contributes to OpenAIRE.</p> <p><i>IBISBAHub already provides dataset cataloguing with the additional benefit of the datasets in context with the projects.</i></p> <p><i>IBISBAHub could be harvested by B2FIND, though the majority of registered assets in IBISBAHub are not open and the harvesting requires mopping to the B2FIND model. B2FIND has poor discovery mechanisms.</i></p>
<p>FAIRsharing</p> <p>https://fairsharing.org</p>	<p>A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies. A technical refresh in Summer 2021 has new APIs. Integrated into the ELIXIR RDMkit and FAIRAssist, a decision making tool for choosing deposition databases, and the ELIXIR Data Stewardship Wizard.</p> <p><i>IBISBAHub should be registered and we should make use of the FAIRsharing collections for standards and deposition databases for EU-IBISBA projects.</i></p>
<p>European Data Portal²⁷⁴</p>	<p>Provides access to open data from international, EU, national, regional, local and geo data portals.</p> <p><i>It's coverage and focus seems to be on harvesting from government portals.</i></p>
<p>EOSCPillar's training and support catalogue²⁷⁵</p>	<p>Based on D4Science research gateway platform (analogous to IBISBAHub) built using the gCube software (analogous to FAIRDOME-SEEK).</p>
<p>Re3data.org</p> <p>https://www.re3data.org/</p> <p>Since 2012, funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG).²⁷⁶</p>	<p>A global registry of research data repositories that covers research data repositories from different academic disciplines. It includes repositories that enable permanent storage of and access to data sets to researchers, funding bodies, publishers, and scholarly institutions. re3data promotes a culture of sharing, increased access and better visibility of research data.</p> <p>Not as curated as FAIRsharing but more comprehensive.</p> <p><i>IBISBAHub should be registered.</i></p>
<p>Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), Security and Privacy preservation</p>	

²⁷³ <http://b2find.eudat.eu/group/inrae>

²⁷⁴ <https://data.europa.eu/en>

²⁷⁵ <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/web/eoscpillartrainingandsupport/catalogue>

²⁷⁶ <http://www.dfg.de/>

The [EOSC Architecture Working Group](#)²⁷⁷, released the [final report](#)²⁷⁸ on the EOSC Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), produced by the EOSC AAI Task Force (TF). The proposed EOSC AAI doesn't set an entirely new AAI architecture, but instead it builds up on outputs of the AARC and AARC2 projects, and especially on the [AARC blueprint architecture](#)²⁷⁹ (BPA), the reference AAI architecture for the international research and education communities.

The AARC-BPA-2019 specifically, proved to be the best starting point for the EOSC AAI, as it focuses on interoperability aspects and introduces the Community AAI, a new concept streamlining researchers' access to services, both provided by their own infrastructure and shared with other communities

B2ACCESS ²⁸⁰ from EUDAT	Authentication and Authorization platform developed by EUDAT. When B2ACCESS is integrated with a given service, the user may log in by using different methods of authentication: Home organisation identity provider; Google account; EUDAT ID EUDAT IDs are created by the B2ACCESS upon registration. B2ACCESS is an Identity Provider for the users that do not have neither a Google account nor a Home Organization Identity Provider. In these cases, B2ACCESS offers a tool for the management of the EUDAT IDs.
EGI Check-In ²⁸¹ from EGI Federation	A proxy service that operates as a central hub to connect federated Identity Providers (IdPs) with EGI service providers. Check-in allows users to select their preferred IdP so that they can access and use EGI services in a uniform and easy way.
GÉANT AAI ²⁸²	GÉANT runs a number of services to support the integration of AAI
ELIXIR-AAI ²⁸³ and LS-Login ²⁸⁴ Provided by Thematic Research Infrastructures ELIXIR and EOSC-Life	The ELIXIR-AAI enables researchers to use their home organisation credentials or community or commercial identities (e.g. ORCID, LinkedIn) to sign in and access data and services they need. It also allows service providers (both in academia and industry) to control and manage access rights of their users and create different access levels for research groups or international projects. The Life Science Login is a AAI system from EOSC-Life. It will supersede the ELIXIR-AAI. <i>The IBISBAHub already implements ELIXIR-AAI, as does the Galaxy workflow infrastructure also used by IBISBA1.o.</i>
<p>Persistent Identifier (PID) Management PID Architecture for the EOSC²⁸⁵ outlines the key role that PIDs play in EOSC and in FAIR. Without mechanisms for universal and persistent identifiers digital objects cannot be referenced and accessed.</p>	

²⁷⁷ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/architecture-working-group>

²⁷⁸ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d1bc3702-61e5-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-188566729>

²⁷⁹ <https://aarc-project.eu/architecture/>

²⁸⁰ <https://b2access.eudat.eu/>

²⁸¹ <https://www.egi.eu/services/check-in/>

²⁸² <https://wiki.geant.org/display/aa1/AAI+Integration+Services>

²⁸³ <https://elixir-europe.org/services/compute/aa1-documentation>

²⁸⁴ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login.html>

²⁸⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/31363e6-4f07-11eb-b59f-01aa75ed71a1>

<p>PID Services are technically implemented services to mint and resolve PIDs, PID Systems are the technical hardware and software components that provide these services and a PID Framework describes a governance structure together with the technical infrastructure that allows organizations to implement PID Services for their needs within agreed policies</p> <p>PIDs play an important role in the concept of FAIR Digital Objects which is an abstraction of data by the identification of minimal elements that are to some degree atomic from the perspective of data management and reuse.</p>	
<p>B2HANDLE ²⁸⁶ Provided by EUDAT</p>	<p>A distributed service for minting, storing, managing and accessing persistent identifiers (PIDs) and essential metadata (PID records) as well as managing PID namespaces. Based on the Handle.net system.</p>
<p>DataCite ²⁸⁷ Organisations within the research community join DataCite as members to be able to assign DOIs to all their research outputs. more than 200 members. Member of the DOI Foundation and uses DOIs as persistent identifiers. The DOI Foundation ²⁸⁸ is a non-profit membership organisation. DOIs use the handle system for PID resolution, and this service is provided for all DOIs by CNRI, which provides a globally distributed network of about 50 proxy servers.</p>	<p>Leading global non-profit organisation that provides PIDs for research data and other research outputs. Based on the Handle.net system. DOIs have to be paid for, and can only be issued by a DOI member <i>DOIs are supported by the FAIRDOM-SEEK platform underpinning the IBISBAHub and minted by IBISBAHub for any of its content. The DOI issuer is The University of Manchester Library.</i></p>
<p>The ePIC Persistent Identifier Consortium for eResearch ²⁸⁹</p>	<p>International consortium of currently nine members that signed a contract to provide a reliable Handle-based PID infrastructure for research data.</p>
<p>The URN PID Framework ²⁹⁰ IANA is the central namespace authority for URN framework. It maintains the registry of URN namespaces at IANA17.</p>	<p>In the URN framework prefixes and namespaces are used to ensure the uniqueness of the PIDs and local PID services are provided to register/modify PIDs and resolve PIDs based on these prefixes. DOI and Handle do not have formal URN namespaces but Handle resolver has already been modified so that it can resolve DOIs and Handles expressed as URNs (e.g. <a href="https://doi.org/urn:doi:<doi>">https://doi.org/urn:doi:<doi>).</p>
<p>The ARK PID Framework ²⁹¹ Archival Resource Key (ARK)</p>	<p>The ARK Alliance is an open global community supporting the ARK infrastructure on behalf of research and scholarship.</p> <p>Since 2001 some 8.2 billion ARKs have been created by over 780 organizations ²⁹². Open, mainstream, non-paywalled, decentralized PIDs that identify anything digital, physical, or abstract. ARKs are similar to DOIs, URNs, and Handles except they are ARKs are cheaper, more flexible, and less centralized.</p>

²⁸⁶ <https://www.eudat.eu/catalogue/B2HANDLE>

²⁸⁷ <https://datacite.org/>

²⁸⁸ <https://www.doi.org/>

²⁸⁹ <https://www.pidconsortium.net/>

²⁹⁰ <https://www.iana.org/assignments/urn-namespaces/urn-namespaces.xhtml>

²⁹¹ <https://arks.org/>

²⁹² <https://arks.org/community/>

	<p>Unlimited identifiers can be created without paying for the right to do so. So they are popular when you need to mint a lot of PIDs, some of which will become DOIs.</p>
<p>ORCID²⁹³ A global, not-for-profit organization sustained by fees from member organizations.²⁹⁴</p>	<p>A persistent digital identifier (an ORCID iD) that researchers own and control, and that distinguishes them from every other researcher. iD connects with professional information — affiliations, grants, publications, peer review, and more. Use the iD to share information with other systems. <i>Widely used by scholarly communications community. IBISBAHub supports ORCID IDs, and is a strong candidate for an identifier for EU-IBISBA users</i></p>
<p>Research Organization Registry²⁹⁵</p>	<p>A community-led project to develop an open, sustainable, usable, and unique identifier for every research organization in the world. <i>IBISBAHub supports ROR</i></p>
<p>Resource Identification Portal²⁹⁶ Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs)</p>	<p>Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) are persistent and unique identifiers for referencing a research resource Used to allocated identifiers to software, mice, instruments etc</p>
<p>Identifiers.org The Identifiers.org Resolution Service Hosted by the EMBL-EBI ELIXIR FAIR Data Service</p>	<p>Provides re-usable identifiers for any data used in the biomedical sciences. It provides resolvable (dereferenceable) URIs for existing database identifiers, which are intended to be stable over time and independent of the provider. This allows the data to “live on” should the provider change, move, or cease support. Many biological databases therefore choose to use identifiers.org for their “official” URIs - for example, Reactome. For database providers, this route can be a easy and maintenance-free way of providing persistent URIs for your data. The Identifiers.org Resolution Service provides consistent access to life science data using Compact Identifiers²⁹⁷. Compact Identifiers consist of an assigned unique prefix and a local provider designated accession number (prefix:accession). The resolving location of Compact Identifiers is determined using information that is stored in the Identifiers.org Registry²⁹⁸.</p>

²⁹³ <https://orcid.org/>

²⁹⁴ <https://info.orcid.org/members>

²⁹⁵ <https://ror.org/>

²⁹⁶ <https://scicrunch.org/resources>

²⁹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2010/NOTE-curie-20101216/>

²⁹⁸ <https://registry.identifiers.org/>